

ODYSSEUS

Unobtrusive Technologies for Secure and Seamless Border Crossing for Travel Facilitation

D6.1

Dissemination, Communication, Exploitation and Stakeholders Engagement Report

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Abstract	The D6.1 deliverable describes the dissemination and communication actions during the first six months of the ODYSSEUS project. A logo, complete brand book, website, social media accounts, leaflet and a general presentation of the project are already prepared and shared to all partners to raise awareness, attract, and engage stakeholders and ensure that the appropriate opportunities and results will be achieved. For efficiently monitoring and reporting our project dissemination and communication activities, a 3-year roadmap that includes press releases, publications, newsletters, and online media engagement has been prepared to present partners efforts and contribution in a well-organized manner.
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2.0	15/10/2024	SIM	Final submitted version

Executive Summary

The ODYSSEUS Project's initiatives are designed to provide passengers and border officials with better travel experiences while preserving security and monitoring movements across land and water among EU countries.

As a result, a clear communication and dissemination strategy is critical for raising public awareness of the benefits of the project among the target audiences and thereby ensuring the successful development of its results.

This document describes analytically the dissemination activities that make up the dissemination strategy and took place during the first six months of ODYSSEUS project. This report also includes future activities that will happen in the coming months until ODYSSEUS completion. It also specifies how ODYSSEUS responds to the requirement set out in the Grant Agreement (GA section 2.2.1) *“Dissemination, communication and exploitation activities, including proper and careful management of IPR and data, will be essential to ensure the successful achievement of ODYSSEUS’s objectives.”*

The structure of the document is the following: After an introduction to document’s goal and mission in Chapter 1, the Dissemination and Communication strategy elements are presented. To communicate the ODYSSEUS idea, objectives, and results to the public, the creation of the brand and specific materials, such as templates, the project's presentation, the leaflet and rollup banner, are crucial for performing the successful dissemination and communication activities and all thoroughly explained and depicted in Chapter 2. Chapter 3 explains the communication channels which are the website and social media and the idea behind their design and content.

The issuing of press releases and launching dedicated Newsletters, as well as the concept guiding the selection of events, workshops and webinars where partners can participate to in order to spread the awareness of ODYSSEUS for the project’s impact to the right target audiences, are well described in Chapter 4. In the same chapter the external meetings and their outcome are mentioned as well as the meetings between the consortium partners and the reason for them are covered. The dissemination activities from all partners that comprise a 3-year roadmap are also included. Clustering with other projects and the target audience are part of Chapter 4 too along with the Key Performance Indicators and how they measure the performance of the Dissemination activities.

Chapter 5 contains all information about the methods to build up the Stakeholder Community and Chapter 6 covers all the process and information of the Standardisation activities. Chapter 7 provides all the details for the Exploitation of the ODYSSEUS project and expands the network of acquaintances.

The conclusions of this document and the outlook for future dissemination is presented in Chapter 8.

A set of annexes are also included in this document, comprising: (a) the Dissemination Procedures; (b) the first Press Release.

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Terms and Abbreviations

BM	Border Management
CERIS	Civil Security for Society
DC	Dissemination and Communication
DCT	Digital Travel Credential
EC	European Commission
ENISA	European Union Agency for Cybersecurity
HE	Horizon Europe
ICAO	International Civil Aviation Organization
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
ISO	International Organization for Standardisation
LEA	Law Enforcement Agencies
eMRTD	Electronic Machine Readable Travel Document
NTWG	New Technologies Working Group
OA	Open Access
PCT	Project Coordination Team
SAB	Security Advisory Board
WP	Work Package

1 INTRODUCTION

The Dissemination, Communication, Exploitation, and Stakeholders Engagement Report is a key deliverable of the ODYSSEUS project, an EU-funded initiative focused on border management. This report serves as a foundational document for the project, providing a comprehensive overview of all activities undertaken thus far in the realm of dissemination, communication, exploitation, and stakeholder engagement. As the first report of its kind, it sets the groundwork for future efforts and showcases the progress made in these crucial areas.

By documenting all the activities performed up to this point, the report provides an important reference point for project partners, stakeholders, and interested parties. It offers valuable insights into the project's progression and achievements.

The report highlights the diverse range of dissemination channels utilized by the ODYSSEUS project, participation in events, future publications, online platforms, and social media. It emphasizes the project's commitment to reaching a wide audience and effectively conveying project objectives, methodologies, and outcomes. It serves as a valuable resource for project partners, stakeholders, and interested parties seeking insights into the project's dissemination and engagement strategies.

Furthermore, it is important to highlight that this report also outlines the plans for the upcoming stakeholder mapping activities. As the ODYSSEUS project progresses, it is essential to continuously update and expand the understanding of the stakeholder landscape. In the forthcoming stages, the project will conduct in-depth research to identify new stakeholders, assess their interests and needs, and determine their potential contributions to the project. The insights gained from this ongoing stakeholder mapping will enhance the project's ability to effectively engage with a broader network of stakeholders, fostering stronger collaborations and ensuring that the project's outcomes align with the evolving needs of the border management community.

Overall, this report highlights the ODYSSEUS project's dedication to promoting border management innovations, fostering collaboration, and ensuring the successful integration of developed solutions into practice. It sets the stage for future endeavours and serves as a guide for the project's continued success in these critical areas.

Finally, the intended readership of this deliverable includes project partners, stakeholders, policymakers, industry representatives, research institutions, and anyone interested in the dissemination, communication, exploitation, and stakeholders' engagement aspects of the ODYSSEUS project. By providing a comprehensive overview of all activities performed until now, this report establishes a strong foundation for the project, ensuring that the general public is well-informed about the project's advancements, contributing to increased transparency and effective collaboration.

2 BRAND IDENTITY & PRINTED MATERIAL

For the ODYSSEUS project, a robust brand identity has been crafted to cater to the project's communication and distribution requirements. This involved the development of comprehensive brand guidelines by a skilled graphic designer, ensuring that ODYSSEUS leaves a lasting visual impression, remains memorable, and stands out in the audience's perception. Following these brand guidelines, a captivating logo, professionally designed templates, an engaging leaflet, and a visually striking rollup banner have been meticulously created.

To facilitate seamless access and utilization of ODYSSEUS dissemination materials, a centralized content repository has been established. All ODYSSEUS dissemination material is available to consortium partners through the content repository.

[Alfresco » Document Library \(simavi.ro\)](#)

All consortium partners are encouraged to make full use of the ODYSSEUS dissemination materials and leverage the established brand identity to amplify the project's impact in the target community.

2.1 LOGO

The ODYSSEUS logo has been shared to the consortium in M2 (February 2023). As shown in Figure 1 the logo is composed by the symbol design and the logotype in a vertical orientation. The symbol design features a circle adorned with three curved lines, representing the pilot use cases within the project. The circular shape, reminiscent of the letter 'O' in ODYSSEUS, embodies the concepts of movement and control. The two colours of the logo are blue and green which are the main colours of the palette of the brand guidelines discussed in the following section 2.2.

Overall, the ODYSSEUS logo encapsulates the essence of the project, symbolizing its collaborative nature, adaptability, and commitment to achieving seamless border crossing.

Figure 1: ODYSSEUS logotype

2.2 BRAND GUIDELINES

The Brand Guidelines, as well as the logo, were submitted to the consortium in M2 (February 2023). These comprehensive guidelines serve to standardize the application of the logo, as well as the usage of colours and fonts. They provide clear instructions on the correct usage of the logo, which is invaluable in ensuring high-quality results, particularly materials. In order to maintain the integrity of the brand identity of ODYSSEUS project and what it represents, it is important to follow the guidelines properly and consistently across all the communication materials. Consistency is key in maintaining a strong and recognizable brand presence.

All consortium members will implement the Brand Guidelines in their respective communication efforts. By doing so, we will reinforce the visual impact and recognition of the project across various channels.

2.2.1 Logo application

The ODYSSEUS logo should be versatile and adaptable to various situations. In order to ensure its successful usage, we have provided not only the colour version but also two monochrome versions: one in white and another in black. These monochrome versions are specifically designed to maintain the visual impact and legibility of the logo, even in scenarios where colour reproduction may be limited or unavailable. By having these additional options, we ensure that the ODYSSEUS logo can maintain its brand identity and recognition across different platforms, media, and printing techniques.

Colour (Figure 2): The main version logo for use on a white background for a greater effect and clarity. Used on all occasions except from the ones it is not possible.

White (Figure 3): This format is used to keep the logo visible in multicolour photos when the colours are dark.

Black (Figure 4): This version should be used when the background is of light colours.

Figure 2: ODYSSEUS logo
Colour format

Figure 3: ODYSSEUS logo
White format

Figure 4: ODYSSEUS logo
Black format

The logo should always appear intact and complete. The minimum size, shown in Figure 5 has been attentively selected making sure that the ODYSSEUS logo is accurately depicted in smaller sizes. At minimum size, the logo is still readable and

instantly recognizable. In case a lower printing technique is used such as screen printing, it is strongly advised to use the logo in a larger size. The proportions and positioning of the elements making up the logo have been chosen thoroughly.

Figure 5: ODYSSEUS logo Minimum size

The ODYSSEUS logo should be displayed only in the forms specified in the Brand Guidelines. The logo may not appear in any other colour other than the original and the monochromes black and white. Neither should be stretched, rotated, or redesigned in any way. Examples of incorrect logo usage can be observed in Figure 6.

Figure 6: ODYSSEUS logo Incorrect use

2.2.2 Colour Palette

The ODYSSEUS Brand Guidelines include the colour palette in Figure 7 with two main and two additional colours. The primary colour, blue, is associated with open spaces, trust, and stability. On the other hand, the green colour represents the diverse range of methods and approaches used to facilitate seamless border crossings. It is created by blending various colours together, symbolizing the project's inclusive and adaptable nature. In addition to the main colours, the Brand Guidelines also introduce two additional colours, red and yellow. The two additional colours can be applied to layouts and creations including website, posters, leaflets and more. These colours should not replace the official colours of the logo.

ODYSSEUS

MAIN COLOURS, BLUE & GREEN

R 4 G 4 B 143
#04048f
C 100 M 100 Y 10 K 10

R 28 G 125 B 115
#1c7d73
C 85 M 30 Y 60 K 10

ADDITIONAL COLOURS, RED & YELLOW

R 141 G 8 B 1
#8d0801
C 30 M 100 Y 100 K 30

R 244 G 213 B 141
#f4d58d
C 0 M 15 Y 50 K 0

LOGOTYPE **BLACK&WHITE** *version*

Figure 7: ODYSSEUS Colour palette

By adhering to the specified colour palette, we can maintain a unified and recognizable visual presence throughout ODYSSEUS communication materials. This will help strengthen the brand identity and enhance the impact of ODYSSEUS messaging across different platforms and mediums.

2.2.3 Fonts

Montserrat font family, a sans-serif typeface with high readability, was chosen for the ODYSSEUS project. Consisting of nine weights from Thin to Black depicted in Figure 8, it is a very adaptable font that may be used for a wide range of purposes due to the geometric and elegant simplicity with nice, rounded shape. Whether it is for headings, body text, or other design elements, Montserrat seamlessly integrates into our project's visual identity. As a google font it is safe for web, meaning it will be displayed correctly in all browsers and devices when visiting the ODYSSEUS website. For the ODYSSEUS logo, we have utilized the Montserrat Bold variant to create a strong and distinctive visual representation of our project. In templates, the overview presentation, and printed materials, we have incorporated various types from the Montserrat font family. This diversity adds visual interest and maintains consistency throughout our project's communication materials.

MONTERRAT BOLD

Montserrat Bold
is used for
headlines and
statements.

TYPEFACE FAMILY

Montserrat Thin
Montserrat ExtraLight
Montserrat Light
Montserrat Medium
Montserrat Regular
Montserrat SemiBold
Montserrat Bold
Montserrat ExtraBold
Montserrat Black

Figure 8: ODYSSEUS Typeface

2.3 PROJECT TEMPLATES

In order to ensure consistency and adherence to the project's brand identity, a set of templates has been developed for various project-related materials within the ODYSSEUS project. For the creation of Deliverables, Presentations, Press Releases, and more, templates have been created in Word and PowerPoint following the brand guidelines explained in Section 2.2. The current document is based on the relevant template.

Additionally, templates for ODYSSEUS meeting agendas and meeting minutes have been prepared to be used for internal coordination meetings. These templates provide a structured framework for organizing and documenting discussions, decisions, and action points.

All ODYSSEUS templates can be easily found by the consortium partners under the project's common repository:

[Alfresco » Document Library \(simavi.ro\)](#)

It is important to note that all templates include the appropriate EU acknowledgement, in compliance with the requirements stipulated by the European Commission and the HORIZON programme. This ensures proper recognition of the project's funding source.

2.4 PROJECT GENERAL PRESENTATION

The ODYSSEUS General Presentation, a key component of our project's dissemination efforts, was successfully completed and distributed to the ODYSSEUS consortium in M4 (April 2023). It has been developed in accordance with the relevant project template whose design follows the brand guidelines. This presentation was created to assist partners in presenting the project's main concept, objectives, consortium, ecosystem, advanced supporting technologies and expected results on every appropriate occasion such as external events, conferences, workshops and more, enabling us to effectively showcase the project's progress and achievements. This presentation (Figure 9) will remain dynamic and continuously updated throughout the entire duration of the project.

Figure 9: ODYSSEUS General Presentation

2.5 PROJECT LEAFLETS

ACC has professionally designed the ODYSSEUS project leaflet (Figure 10) keeping in line with the brand guidelines and making sure the key points of the project could be promptly understood. The initial version of this leaflet in A4 has been circulated to the consortium in M4 (April 2023) providing partners with a comprehensive overview of the project. Additionally, a condensed version in A5 size was shared with partners in M5 (May 2023) and it was strongly recommended that all partners print, distribute, or display the A5 leaflet at any relevant event. The leaflet contains consortium details, ODYSSEUS project description, objectives and expected impact. It also includes explicit graphical representations of three real-life scenarios and features the EU acknowledgement.

As the Pilot Use Cases progress and results become available, we anticipate updating the leaflet to include images showcasing the outcomes. This will further enhance the leaflet's effectiveness in conveying the project's progress and achievements.

By disseminating this comprehensive leaflet, we aim to increase awareness and understanding of the ODYSSEUS project among various stakeholders.

Project Facts

Work programme: Horizon.2.3
Topic: HORIZON-CL3-2021-BM-01-03
Funded under: Civil Security for Society
Duration: 36 months | Starting from 1 January 2023
Total cost: €4.59 million
Coordinator: SOFTWARE IMAGINATION & VISION SRL

Unobtrusive Technologies for Secure and Seamless Border Crossing for Travel Facilitation

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[@odysseus_heu](https://twitter.com/odysseus_heu)

Consortium

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23/9/23 8:14 µs

About ODYSSEUS

ODYSSEUS is a 3-year, Horizon funded project consisting of 14 partners from all over Europe and the United Kingdom aiming to improve border crossing experience for travelers and border authorities' staff, while maintaining security and monitoring of movements across land and sea EU external borders.

ODYSSEUS will provide a holistic framework for improving border checks performed by the authorities and facilitate travelling for citizens. A combination of strong multi-behavioral and biometric continuous user identity verification mechanisms will ensure the identification of the citizens, allowing them to cross the border without any interruption or queue. In the meantime, a novel luggage and baggage check will allow citizens' vehicles and cargos to be remotely checked on the land border in terms of goods and thus speed up the border check processes in a secure and reliable manner. The ODYSSEUS platform will be applicable for both land and water scenarios including on the road, in a maritime port, and in the train.

Expected impact

- Improved border crossing experience for travelers and border authorities, while maintaining security and monitoring of movements across EU external borders.
- Improved security of EU land, air borders, sea borders and the maritime environment, against accidents, natural disasters, and security challenges.
- Improved customs and supply chain security through better prevention, detection, deterrence, and fight of illegal activities. Improve situational awareness, decision making and reaction for both land and maritime border control by utilizing bespoke visual analytics tools and multimodal data fusion.

Project Objectives

DESIGN and DEVELOP a unifying platform that enables seamless, fully non-stop border crossing in a highly secure manner, assisting Law Enforcement Agencies (LEA) with automated, reliable, and accurate border checks, while improving the travelling experience for EU citizens in a privacy-preserving way.

ADVANCE the identification and control capabilities of Border Authorities through robust and reliable identity verification mechanisms introducing an EU mobile (virtual) passport protected by continuous behavioral authentication.

IMPROVE border control checks without stopping cargos and vehicles through safe, unobtrusive, and portable screening based on X-ray backscatter technology, UAV-assisted image processing and AI-based data analytics.

VALIDATE the effectiveness of the proposed ODYSSEUS platform through its demonstration in real-life environments with the active engagement and training of security practitioners in two diverse landscapes and various operational environments (inside a train, on the road, onboard a ship in a port area).

SPEED UP the rapid uptake by relevant security stakeholders of the ODYSSEUS innovations through wide communication, scientific dissemination and targeted commercial exploitation activities coupled with contributions to relevant standardisation bodies.

Pilot Activities

The ODYSSEUS solution will be tested, validated, and demonstrated in three real operational scenarios selected for their high societal economic and security impact on the EU citizens and the Border Authorities. The foreseen scenarios include **seamless border crossing on Land, Sea, and Train.**

ODYSSEUS_leaflet_A6_v2.indd 4-5
23/9/23 8:15 µs

Figure 10: ODYSSEUS Leaflet

2.6 PROJECT ROLLUP BANNER

The Project Roll-up banner (Figure 11) has been also created and distributed within the consortium in M5 (May 2023) showcasing an eye-catching design that aims to make a significant impact during events and conferences attended by ODYSSEUS project partners.

This traditional Rollup banner provides a concise overview of the project's highlights at a glance. Its purpose is to captivate the audience's attention and promote the project through a combination of informative text and visually appealing elements.

The design ties in with all dissemination material since it complies with the brand standards. The Logo is placed at the top to be clearly visible from a distance along with the main title. The brief description of ODYSSEUS and the QR linked to the website, are placed wisely at the eye level to the left. Next, the project facts are prominent and an infographic displaying all technologies follows. Towards the bottom of the banner, the pilot cases, social media channels, partners' logos, and the necessary EU acknowledgment are cleverly positioned.

By utilizing this visually appealing and descriptive Roll-up banner, the ODYSSEUS project aims to maximize its impact during events, leaving a lasting impression on the audience and effectively conveying the project's objectives and achievements.

ODYSSEUS

Unobtrusive Technologies for Secure and Seamless Border Crossing for Travel Facilitation

Seamless, Secure Border Crossing. Enhancing border checks, traveler experience, and law enforcement efficiency. Advanced identity verification, mobile passport, and cutting-edge screening technologies. Demonstrating effectiveness in real-life environments for rapid adoption by border management stakeholders.

Project Facts | **Duration:** 36 months | **Project Coordinator:** Ms Monica Florea, SIMAVI - Software Imagination & Vision
Start Date: 1st January 2023
Total cost: €4.59 million

Technologies

Digital and Virtual Passport | Vehicle Scanning X-Ray Technologies | Faceless GDPR Compliant Travellers Counting

Seamless Identity Verification | AI-powered Behavioural Authentication | UAV-Assisted Vehicle Scanning | Multi-Modal Fusion and DSS equipped X-AI

PILOTS

TRAIN | LAND | WATER

Consortium

SIMAVI | Rapiscan systems | AS&E | quadible | Telesio Technologies | vision-box | ISIG | UIC

ACCUELDENCE | SQUAREDEV | THALES | European Union

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Figure 11: ODYSSEUS Rollup banner

3 COMMUNICATION CHANNELS

3.1 PROJECT WEBSITE

The ODYSSEUS website was launched in M4 (April 2023). Prior to its launch, a holding webpage (Figure 12) was available from the beginning of the project. This page featured the project logo, full title, links to ODYSSEUS social media accounts, the EU emblem, and an acknowledgement of the EC contribution.

The ODYSSEUS fully functional website (Figure 13) is available at the address <https://odysseusproject.eu/>. The graphic layout has been meticulously designed to ensure consistency with the project's brand. An additional feature is the accessibility toolbar on the website's right side. This toolbar allows visitors with visual impairments to customize their browsing experience by adjusting font settings, enlarging text size, and selecting the optimal colour contrast for easier content readability.

The primary objective of the ODYSSEUS website is to raise awareness about the project and its impact while facilitating collaboration and knowledge exchange among project partners and stakeholders. By constantly updating the content of the pages with new information it becomes a one-stop-shop for ODYSSEUS' latest updates, a living platform for sharing resources. Visitors can easily get in touch by utilizing the contact form and stay informed about project activities and progress by subscribing to the Newsletter form, which is connected to the Mailchimp platform. In addition, the inclusion of links to ODYSSEUS social media accounts encourages visitors to become followers and engage with the project on various platforms.

In the footer of the website, alongside the EU acknowledgement, there are three button links that direct users to legal documents outlining the website 's policies. To provide secure connection between the website and potential visitors, only Hyper Transfer Protocol Secure (HTTPS) is used to access the website.

Figure 12: ODYSSEUS splash page

Figure 13: ODYSSEUS website

3.1.1 Website Structure

The Worldwide Web, also referred to as the Web, has become the most common source of information. The website serves as a tool for organizing and presenting textual and multimedia material, as well as for expanding the audience of interested parties and ensuring the project's long-term viability.

The website's logo and primary navigation menu are prominently displayed at the top, ensuring easy access for visitors. At the bottom of the website, the EU emblem is showcased, along with an acknowledgement of the EC's contribution to the project. Additionally, links to the legal documents such as the Data Privacy Policy, the Cookies Policy, and the Web Imprint to assure that the General Data Protection Regulation requirements are met. Visitors to the website are given the required information regarding the processing of their personal data via the website (such as a contact form) in line with article 13 GDPR. When a user visits the website, a banner is displayed to ask the visitor for their consent to the use of cookies. The user can browse the site regardless of whether they approve or reject the cookie consent.

The website is only accessible via Hyper Transfer Protocol Secure (HTTPS) which guarantees secure communication between the website and potential visitors.

By implementing these measures, the website maintains a user-friendly experience while adhering to legal obligations and respecting user privacy.

The structure of the ODYSSEUS **website sitemap** is the following:

1. HOMEPAGE

2. PROJECT

- Overview
- Structure
- Objectives
- Pilot Use Cases
- Targeted Audiences

3. CONSORTIUM

4. COLLABORATION

- Sister Projects
- H2020 BES Cluster

5. RESOURCES

- Publications
- PU Deliverables

6. COMMUNICATIONS

- News & Events
- Newsletters
- Press Releases
- Media Kit

7. CONTACT

The numbered and bulleted items above can be navigated through the menu bar at the top of the site. Additional information on the various sections of the website is provided below.

3.1.1.1 Homepage

A slider containing a significant image and the project's complete title is present on the Homepage. A short description text about the project follows and subsequent to that an infographic depicting project facts. Further below is a section including three cards, each one of them explaining the expected impact of the ODYSSEUS project and so on the technologies depicted with their titles and relevant icons. Next, all partners logos with the relevant links to their official websites and the section with the Newsletter form along with a phrase prompting users to subscribe follows. The last part includes the link to the ODYSSEUS page on Cordis as well as the social media accounts and the contact info for the project.

3.1.1.2 Project

This category provides further information on the project through its subsections about the ODYSSEUS structure, objectives, pilot use cases and targeted audiences. The 7 work packages comprising the structure of the project are separately described in terms of their objectives. The ODYSSEUS objectives are depicted via an infographic in the corresponding subsection. A brief reference in the pilot use cases can be found in the respective subsections which will be fully updated in the future with pilots' actions and their results.

3.1.1.3 Consortium

In this category a geographical map is presented with each partner's logos placed in the corresponding countries. Every partner's logo is linked to their own internal page on the ODYSSEUS website. Each partner's dedicated page contains their information and describes their role in ODYSSEUS project. Additionally, all available social media accounts are incorporated.

3.1.1.4 Collaboration

This category is comprised of two subsections, the sister Projects which are still in their early stages and will be presented in the next months and the H2020 BES Cluster. The later subsection contains a text explaining the reasons for ODYSSEUS joining the H2020 BES Cluster and a quick synopsis of what is the purpose and vision of the H2020 BES Cluster. All members with their logos and links to their social media accounts and websites are also presented on this page.

3.1.1.5 Resources

Like the previous category, "Resources" are divided into two subsections: Publications and PU Deliverables. In both sections content will be available upon publication and official acceptance by the EC, respectively.

3.1.1.1.6 Communications

The Communications aspects in this category are presented through four different subsections: News & Events, Newsletters, Press Releases and Media Kit.

The “News & Events” subsection includes the announcements about crucial developments of the project including any Dissemination and Communication activity that occurs, such as a meeting between partners or the publication of articles and communication materials.

The “Newsletter” subsection contains all project newsletters that will be emailed out to the subscribers of the ODYSSEUS mailing list.

The “Press Releases” subcategory has all the press releases ready for view.

The “Media Kit” encompasses the logo, the promotional material (leaflet, roll up banner) and informational content on the brand guidelines.

3.1.1.1.7 Contact

Within the “Contact” category, all the methods you can communicate with the projects are listed. The main contact email address and info is displayed along with a contact form. In both ways, interested website visitors will be able to choose how to contact project members and request additional information or propose potential future collaborations. Links to the Twitter and LinkedIn accounts of the project are also included along with the registration form to the ODYSSEUS Newsletter for visitors who wish to watch the project's development and keep up with its updates.

3.2 SOCIAL MEDIA

The substantial dissemination of the ODYSSEUS project will also be achieved through a carefully planned and managed social media strategy. The official social media accounts of the Project are available on [LinkedIn](#), [Twitter](#) and [YouTube](#) and serve as key platforms for sharing updates and engaging with the public. ACC holds the responsibility of regularly updating these social media accounts, ensuring that postings about partner accomplishments and other relevant public information are shared in a timely manner. To maximize the project's reach, ACC actively encourages all project partners with social media accounts to follow, react, and share coherent content, while consistently tagging and mentioning the ODYSSEUS profile. This collaborative effort strengthens the project's online presence and facilitates wider audience engagement.

3.2.1 LinkedIn

During the initial phase of the project, a dedicated LinkedIn Company page was created for the “ODYSSEUS project” and is available at <https://www.linkedin.com/company/odysseusproject-heu/>. This official page, as shown in Figure 14, serves as a central hub for sharing all major project updates and announcements, ensuring that our followers are well-informed and engaged.

LinkedIn is the most effective social media platform for ODYSSEUS considering it is a professional network where relevant stakeholders can stay informed and actively participate. It serves as an effective tool for sharing content from the ODYSSEUS website, thus increasing its traffic, and retaining interest in the development of the project.

One notable advantage of having a Company LinkedIn page is that it offers additional tools for measuring the overall performance of the activities. These tools enable in-depth data analysis, tracking organic campaign results and providing valuable insights.

By leveraging the capabilities of LinkedIn, ACC aims to maximize the visibility and impact of the ODYSSEUS project within the professional community and beyond.

Figure 14: ODYSSEUS LinkedIn page

As of now, the ODYSSEUS LinkedIn page has 135 followers and ACC has consistently shared valuable updates through 18 engaging posts (Table 1: ODYSSEUS LinkedIn analytics). The first posts focused on introducing the consortium's core partners to our LinkedIn community. News such as the launch

of the first Press Release, the creation of the ODYSSEUS leaflet and rollup banner, the launch of the website and participation in events were also posted on LinkedIn to enhance awareness about the project. Additionally, on notable international observance days such as Women's Day and Mother Earth Day, ODYSSEUS LinkedIn profile remains active, showcasing posts that align with these themes. Through our LinkedIn presence, we aim to foster awareness and engage with our audience on a diverse range of topics related to the project.

Table 1: ODYSSEUS LinkedIn analytics

Post link	Impressions	Clicks	Likes	Engagement rate
https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7037084409279184896	232	16	20	16%
https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7033823827193171968	240	52	17	29%
https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7034472660105342976	283	21	18	14%
https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7039232103347011584	242	9	14	9%
https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7042109294086864896	331	8	24	9%
https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7044662491276029953	302	11	30	14%
https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7044995578962788353	202	8	14	10%

Post link	Impressions	Clicks	Likes	Engagement rate
https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7048646852027531264	233	5	16	8%
https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7052262546040336384	161	1	17	12%
https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7050014558765129728	213	9	16	12%
https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7055095394355032064	248	7	18	9%
https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7055934913992081408	87	1	0	1%
https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7057311960484241408	470	186	34	47%
https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7059071413864796161	367	15	25	11%
https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7061298158047236096	216	4	12	8%
https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7063791645581844480	123	58	12	57%

Post link	Impressions	Clicks	Likes	Engagement rate
https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7067800538528047104	327	8	13	7.03%
https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7072918114094489600	251	8	33	16.73%
https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7074683813368373248	123	7	18	21.14%

3.2.2 Twitter

An official [Twitter account, @ODYSSEUS_heu](#), has been created for the ODYSSEUS project as shown in (Figure 15). ACC will utilize this platform to share the latest information and developments related to the project and the broader field of interest, including updates on the European Commission's latest measures on border management and other relevant projects.

Furthermore, ACC will plan organic efforts to enhance awareness and engagement to the communities for the key milestones.

So far, the ODYSSEUS Twitter account has 17 followers while it is following 18 accounts and has 13 tweets.

Figure 15: ODYSSEUS Twitter page

3.2.3 YouTube

YouTube is the world's most popular video-sharing website, offering a vast platform for sharing and discovering video content. As part of the ODYSSEUS project, two videos will be created to present the concept and solutions offered by the implementation of the project and they will be accessible through the ODYSSEUS YouTube channel, which can be found at [@odysseusproject](#) (Figure 16). ACC took the initiative to establish this channel during the first month of the project, ensuring that it aligns seamlessly with the ODYSSEUS communication strategy. Once the videos are finalized, they will be promptly uploaded to the

channel, making them readily available for viewing by our stakeholders, partners, and the public.

Figure 16: ODYSSEUS YouTube channel

4 DISSEMINATION & COMMUNICATION

4.1 PRESS RELEASES

Throughout the project, press releases will be issued to communicate major project outcomes that have a significant influence on society and/or dedicated communities. These press releases will be published around important milestones to reach end-users and interested professionals through specialised publications and digital media channels. The objective is to generate positive press attention for the project at local, national, and European levels. Task 6.1 Leader will coordinate this effort and the material must be approved in accordance with the already established and detailed approval procedures described in Annex 1: Dissemination Procedures.

The first Press Release, showcased in Annex 2: Press Release, issued by ACC, highlights the successful launch of the ODYSSEUS project. Its purpose is to provide partners with the necessary text, enabling them to inform their contacts about the project's commencement. By sharing this information, partners actively contribute to raising awareness and exerting a significant influence on the project's visibility and impact.

4.2 E-NEWSLETTERS

The ODYSSEUS project aims to enhance its communication and engagement with stakeholders through the release of biannual e-newsletters. These newsletters will provide updates on the project's progress, highlight significant news, and showcase ongoing activities. ODYSSEUS will be releasing a biannual e-newsletter that will describe the growth of the project framework as well as announce interesting news and activities. The [1st Newsletter](#), scheduled for release

in M7 (July 2023), will focus on the evolution of the project framework, initiatives undertaken, and outline future steps. As the project reaches its one-year milestone, the [second newsletter](#), to be sent in M12 (January 2024), will offer an overview of the project's journey in its first year.

4.3 PUBLICATIONS

ODYSSEUS completely complies with the Horizon Europe requirement for Open Access (OA) publishing. Results from ODYSSEUS will be published not only in academic or industry-relevant journals but also in other appropriate mediums to reach a diverse audience and maximize the project's impact. This includes but is not limited to conference proceedings, white papers, technical reports, and online platforms. ACC has already distributed a list of journals for partners to consider for publishing their papers written relevant to the ODYSSEUS advances and results.

To ensure a coordinated and consistent approach to publishing, there is a specific Dissemination Procedure outlined in Annex 1: Dissemination Procedures. When a partner intends to write a paper related to the ODYSSEUS project, it must receive approval from the Project Coordinator, Project Manager, and Project Security Advisory Board (SAB) prior to publication. The partner should inform the Dissemination and Communication (DC) team directly, providing a two-week notice. The DC team promptly communicates this information to the Project Coordinator and SAB, who will review and either approve or reject the activity within five working days. The decision is then conveyed to the partner by the DC team. In the event of any conflicts or objections, a discussion among the involved parties will be initiated to address the matter effectively.

This well-defined procedure ensures that all publications related to ODYSSEUS adhere to the project's guidelines and objectives, fostering transparency and quality in our dissemination efforts.

4.4 EVENTS & WORKSHOPS

ODYSSEUS' participation in conferences, workshops, and exhibitions, as well as invitations to activities such as webinars that ODYSSEUS will host, will be covered in this section. These engagements provide valuable opportunities to showcase the project's progress, exchange knowledge, and foster collaborations with stakeholders. To facilitate partner engagement and create broad awareness about the project, ACC has shared a list of upcoming events aligned with the central idea and goals of ODYSSEUS.

To ensure smooth participation in events and workshops, all partners must adhere to the specific Dissemination Procedure. The participation of any Partner in an event related to ODYSSEUS project has to be approved beforehand by the Project Coordinator, the Project Manager, and the Project Security Advisory Board (SAB). The DC team is informed directly from the partner who wants to participate two weeks prior the event and communicates this to the PCT and SAB who approve or reject this activity within five working days and the DC team informs the

interested partner about the decision. In case of conflict or objection a discussion between the members who take part in the whole procedure.

In case a partner wishes to organize a workshop or special event then the WP6 Leader must be aware two months before the realisation of this type of dissemination activity so as to communicate it to the PCT and SAB Team on time properly.

After attending an event or workshop each partner must fill in the dissemination report available [here](#) and upload it in the repository where the appropriate folder has been created for this purpose and store the photos and snippets from the event [here](#). In that way the DC team can effectively share this Dissemination activity on social media and website to raise awareness and increase engagement of the followers who are updated, and their interest is aroused. The full Dissemination procedures document for events and workshop is available in Annex 1: Dissemination Procedures.

During the first six months of the project, partners from SIMAVI and UIC attended several notable events, presenting ODYSSEUS and engaging in fruitful discussions with industry experts and academic peers. These events served as platforms for disseminating project outcomes, raising awareness about our innovative solutions, and garnering interest from potential collaborators and end-users.

At the early stages of the ODYSSEUS project, SIMAVI participated at the CERIS Workshop: “Methods and examples of piloting and validation of innovative border management solutions” event on the 9th of March 2023 in Brussels where it was engaged in fruitful discussions with other similar project representants.

The ODYSSEUS project was presented at [the 18th UIC World Security Congress](#) held in Jaipur, India from 21 to 23 February 2023. The presentation was conducted by UIC. This globally recognized security platform attracted 100 participants, providing an excellent opportunity to increase publicity and raise awareness about the project's objectives and one of its three pilot use cases—the seamless train border crossing scenario.

SIMAVI also participated in the prestigious conference “[Research and Innovation Symposium for European SECURITY and Defence](#)” (RISE SD 2023) held in Rhodes, Greece from 29 to 31 May 2023. During this international EU research and innovation event, SIM, the ODYSSEUS Project Coordinator, presented the project and participated in two discussion panels for Piloting, Validation and Market Uptake of Innovative solutions relevant to Border Management. Additionally, SIM chaired the Border Management Panel. The audience primarily consisted of stakeholders, as well as industry and technology partners.

Another noteworthy attendance of SIMAVI is in the Policy Seminar (PPS) for Border Management organized by EC for the new HE granted projects on 14-15 June 2023 in Brussels.

By actively engaging in these events, the project's objectives and impact were communicated to a diverse audience, fostering a wider understanding and recognition of ODYSSEUS project.

4.5 INTERNAL MEETINGS

Project Internal Meetings (Table 2: ODYSSEUS Internal Meetings) play a vital role in fostering collaboration and ensuring effective communication within the ODYSSEUS consortium. These meetings allow partners to interact with each other, generate ideas for specific project areas, and keep everyone informed about the status of each work package. To facilitate productive discussions, ACC has developed and shared Meeting Agenda templates, available [here](#), which enable partners to prepare their inputs and questions in advance. Meeting Minutes templates are also available [here](#) for anyone who isn't able to attend and wants to be informed about possible decisions or changes regarding the project.

The ODYSSEUS kick-off meeting, held in Bucharest, Romania, on January 26 and 27, 2023, marked the introduction of core project concepts to all consortium members. The 2nd physical meeting took place in Prague, Czech Republic, on June 26 and 27, 2023. All project partners gathered for this plenary meeting to present all the tangible outcomes from each work package. The team members exchanged views on the project's status and clarified any outstanding issues.

The main project coordination body is the Project Coordination Team (PCT) led by SIMAVI as Project Coordinator. As shown in D1.1 Project Management Handbook, PCT has regular monthly meetings, organised by SIMAVI to discuss the status of ODYSSEUS implementation activities.

Additionally, monthly virtual meetings are conducted by the Work Package (WP) leaders to discuss the progress made in each work package and showcase achievements and results. On May 18, 2023, the WP6 Leader organized the 1st WP6 meeting, bringing together all Task Leaders to address critical project issues and ensure seamless operation across tasks.

Table 2: ODYSSEUS Internal Meetings

Date	Location	Name
26 – 27 Jan 2023	Bucharest, Romania	Kick off meeting
28 Feb 2023	Online	1 st PCT meeting
23 Mar 2023	Online	2 nd PCT meeting
27 Apr 2023	Online	3 rd PCT meeting
09 May 2023	Online	1 st WP6 meeting
18 May 2023	Online	4 th PCT meeting
21 Jun 2023	Online	5 th PCT meeting
26 – 27 Jun 2023	Prague, Czech	Plenary meeting

4.6 PARTNERS’ INDIVIDUAL PLANS

Dissemination materials (a brochure, a roll-up banner, project templates etc.) were developed and delivered to Consortium partners for use in dissemination and communication initiatives. As part of this task, a table (Table 3) showing the contribution of each partner regarding the creation of content on Social Media accounts / Blog posts / Newsletters has been developed by the consortium in order to create a 3-year dissemination and communications roadmap that will be monitored by ACC and entail participation and commitment from all partners.

Table 3: ODYSSEUS Partner’s Individual Plans

Name of Partner	Individual planning (with KPIs)	Type of action*	Status/ Month (Performed or not and when)
SIM	3 Press releases	Press release	1 press release per year 1 st press release done in Feb 2023
	2 Article published in a journal	Writing article for a scientific journal or other publication	2 publications by the end of ODYSSEUS
	3 Social networks posts on SIMAVI's social media channels	-Regular posting on LinkedIn -Social media announcements and digital media posts on Twitter -Digital media posts on Facebook	1 social media post per year 1 st post on SIMAVI's LinkedIn, Twitter and FB accounts done in Feb 2023

Name of Partner	Individual planning (with KPIs)	Type of action*	Status/ Month (Performed or not and when)
	3 materials in SIMAVI's Newsletters	Promotion through internal SIMAVI newsletters	1 post per year
	100 ODYSSEUS Leaflets	ODYSSEUS leaflets distributed per year online	100 Leaflets distributed per year
	Local dissemination activities for ODYSSEUS website	ODYSSEUS website promotion on SIMAVI's website	Continuously until the end of the project
	Organizing a (1) workshop for the project	A workshop for dissemination ODYSSEUS project's results (presentation)	1 workshop by the end of ODYSSEUS
	Contribution to (2) two ODYSSEUS Videos	Video published via the YouTube channel of the project, contribution with other partners	2 until the end of the project
	Dissemination of project's results to (3) three related events and conferences	Face to face or online presentations of ODYSSEUS results	1 per year until the end of the project

Name of Partner	Individual planning (with KPIs)	Type of action*	Status/ Month (Performed or not and when)
VISB	1. Dissemination of the project information in the corporate website	Website	M4
	2. Share/Retweet/Rep post of all social media posts made by the ODYSSEUS social media teams.	Digital Media Posts	M4 to M36
QBE	Dissemination on the company's website	Website	M1-M36
	Attendance to relevant conferences, events, meetups	Events	
	Press release about the project	Press release	
	Dissemination on company's social media feeds	Social media	
TEL	Dissemination of project's results to (2) two events and conferences related with the action	Presentation	2 until the end of project after M12
	Post on TELESTO's social media channels (LinkedIn)	Digital media post	2 posts per year (1 st in M6)
	Digital banner on new TELESTO's web site (under construction)	Digital media post	Continuously until the end of project (From M12)
	Post on TELESTO's newsletter	Digital media post	2 per year (From M12)

Name of Partner	Individual planning (with KPIs)	Type of action*	Status/ Month (Performed or not and when)
	ODYSSEUS leaflets or e-brochures	Leaflets	30 leaflets per year
ACC	<p>Publish the project description on ACC's website to provide an overview of ODYSSEUS and its objectives.</p> <p>Conduct presentations to Greek stakeholders, emphasizing the project's relevance and potential impact.</p> <p>Present ODYSSEUS to Cypriot stakeholders, highlighting the project's benefits.</p> <p>Organize in-house presentations for ACC employees and collaborating partners to enhance internal awareness and engagement.</p> <p>Initiate regular posts on social media platforms to share project updates, milestones, and key findings.</p> <p>Translate and distribute the 1st project press release, increasing visibility and attracting external interest.</p> <p>Deliver presentations on ODYSSEUS in three selected events, targeting relevant industry</p>	<p>ACC is leading the dissemination tasks of the ODYSSEUS project and is responsible for driving all project-based dissemination and communication activities. The company will implement both internal and external dissemination efforts to maximize the project's reach and impact.</p>	M1 – M36

Name of Partner	Individual planning (with KPIs)	Type of action*	Status/ Month (Performed or not and when)
	<p>professionals, researchers, and policymakers.</p> <p>Distribute project leaflets at external events to raise awareness among attendees.</p> <p>Engage with the BES cluster to establish connections, share knowledge, and identify collaboration opportunities.</p> <p>Develop technical texts highlighting ACC's role and contributions to ODYSSEUS for publication on the project's official website.</p> <p>Collaborate with project partners to produce a comprehensive project report, including ACC's contributions.</p>		
SQD	<p>Dissemination activities:</p> <p>1) Qualitive Aspects</p> <p>Social Media Engagement.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Share project updates, news, and achievements in LinkedIn. Encourage engagement with the project by responding to comments, questions, and feedback. 	Online Dissemination Activities	<p>Throughout the lifetime of the project will be posted all the results, updates, and achievements.</p> <p>Indicative plan:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> LinkedIn posts: M8, M10, M12, M14, M16, M18, M20,

Name of Partner	Individual planning (with KPIs)	Type of action*	Status/ Month (Performed or not and when)
	<p>Upload the project activities and results in SQD's official site.</p> <p>2) Quantitative Aspects</p> <p>Social Media Engagement (KPIs):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of likes (>100), shares (> 20), comments (>10) and reposts of each of SQD's posted actions in LinkedIn. 		<p>M22, M24, M26, M28, M30, M32, M34 and M36</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The projects' activities and first results will be published in SQD's official site on M10. Will be updated based on the most significant results of the project. <p>1)LinkedIn post, Title: "Odysseus project website", Date: 06/06/2023, link: https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7071828589528104960</p> <p>Details until 06/06/2023: 23 impressions, 6 reactions, 26.09% engagement rate</p>

Name of Partner	Individual planning (with KPIs)	Type of action*	Status/ Month (Performed or not and when)
THALES	Dissemination on the company’s website	Website	M1-M36

Name of Partner	Individual planning (with KPIs)	Type of action*	Status/ Month (Performed or not and when)
	Dissemination within Thales technical and Border Control expert community (2 presentations, more than 100 participants)	Presentations	
ISIG	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Press Releases. ▪ ISIG website news Social Media Communication Activities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Press releases ▪ Article on ISIG’s website – news section ▪ Social Media Communication Activities: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Facebook posts regarding project activities and meetings; ○ LinkedIn posts regarding project activities 	2 – M15 1 – M12 1 – M1 4/year

Name of Partner	Individual planning (with KPIs)	Type of action*	Status/ Month (Performed or not and when)
		s and meetings.	
RBP	Dissemination and communication actions during the ODYSSEUS project	Tweet/Retweet	Realised/ May-June Post on Twitter
IGPF MAI	Dissemination and communication actions during the ODYSSEUS project	IGPF MAI website	M1-M36
CDBP	At least 3 times	Publication an information about the projects and its implementation on the website of CDBP	Not performed yet/ yearly- 2023-2025
BBA	<p>ODYSSEUS Leaflet taped at the entrance to the Bureau of Border and Foreign Police building.</p> <p>Communication actions: 2 ODYSSEUS slides will be included to presentation at the</p>	<p>Visible for 200 persons per working day</p> <p>Presentation</p>	<p>Since May 2023</p> <p>Continuously</p>

Name of Partner	Individual planning (with KPIs)	Type of action*	Status/ Month (Performed or not and when)
	<p>meetings/workshops abroad.</p> <p>Social media: ODYSSEUS website will be published on the Facebook profile of the Police Force</p>	<p>3,700,000+ unique visitors viewed Facebook profile in 2022</p>	<p>Continuously</p>
<p>UIC</p>	<p>Communication actions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> One ODYSSEUS slide in the presentation given at the UIC World Security Congress (Jaipur, India) and entitled “UIC Security Research Projects: A decade of innovative results and way forward.” Audience: 100 participants from 23 countries from Asia, Africa, North America, Europe, and the Middle East (railway security managers, transport and police authorities, and United Nations and Interpol). One press release published in 3 languages to an audience of 610 	<p>Presentation</p> <p>Press release</p> <p>Press release</p>	<p>M2 – Feb. 2023 (completed)</p> <p>M3 – March 2023 (completed)</p> <p>To be published after major project events</p> <p>Planned regular publication after each project event</p>

Name of Partner	Individual planning (with KPIs)	Type of action*	Status/ Month (Performed or not and when)
	<p>international or English-speaking journalists, 110 German-speaking journalists, and 200 francophone journalists: https://uic.org/com/IMG/pdf/press_release_ODYSSEUS.pdf</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Other press releases <p>UIC eNews articles (electronic newsletter) published to 3000 contacts: UIC members, partners organisations, industries</p>	Digital media posts	
RAPI	<p>Guest speaker for RAPI monthly online meeting called Punday</p> <p>PEN-CP, the Pan-European Network of Customs Practitioners – EU Horizon 2020 funded Customs security practitioner project</p>	Meeting (Presentation)	Not Performed/Nov 2023
	Dynamic Energy thresholding with SiPMs	Patent	In Process / Oct 2023
	Dynamic Energy thresholding with SiPMs	Publication	Not Performed / Jan 2024

Name of Partner	Individual planning (with KPIs)	Type of action*	Status/ Month (Performed or not and when)
	Object detection algorithms in occupied vehicles operating at ultra-low doses	Publication	Not Performed / July 2024
	ICBPMS 2024: Border Protection and Management Studies Conference, Barcelona (Feb 11-12, 2024)	Conference (Sponsorship, stand, presentation, conference proceedings)	Not Performed / Feb 2024
	ICBPMS 2024: Border Protection and Management Studies Conference, Barcelona (Feb 11-12, 2024)	Conference (Sponsorship, stand, presentation)	Not Performed / Feb 2024
	International Conference on Border Security Studies ICBSS on March 15-16, 2024, in London, United Kingdom	Conference (Sponsorship, stand, presentation, conference proceedings)	Not Performed / March 2024

4.7 CLUSTERING WITH OTHER PROJECTS - UPDATED

Networking with other associated EU-projects is of paramount importance as it facilitates knowledge exchange among professionals working in the same sector, enabling them to collectively address common challenges. This will help to eliminate overlaps and avoid duplication of efforts, as well as accelerate progress in the field without delays. During M3 (March 2023) the [ODYSSEUS project joined the H2020 BES Cluster](#) in order to exchange information, plan outreach initiatives, solicit assistance, and publicise project activity.

The H2020 BES Cluster is composed of projects working together to support one another, identify solutions to upcoming challenges, ensure effective

dissemination and valuable exploitation potentials, and simultaneously generate knowledge that will change the current state in the fields and areas the projects are working on.

ODYSSEUS consortium aims to leverage synergies, strengthen the project's impact, and contribute to a collective and cohesive approach in addressing border security challenges.

To actively engage in clustering activities, all partners will proactively identify and connect with projects that share similar goals, target audiences, or thematic areas. We will seek opportunities to participate in relevant networks, conferences, and workshops where we can interact with other projects and explore collaboration possibilities. Through these clustering efforts, we aim to foster a dynamic and collaborative environment that accelerates progress, encourages innovation, and maximizes the impact of the project.

SIMAVI represented ODYSSEUS Consortium in the global Conference **“Research and Innovation Symposium for European SECURITY and Defense” RISE SD 2023**, that took place in Rhodes, Greece, between 29-31 May 2023 where she presented the ODYSSEUS project and chaired the Board Management Panel. SIMAVI actively participated in two discussion panels where bilateral conversations with representants of similar project took place.

SIMAVI will continue its efforts together with ACC to establish links with the other sister projects of ODYSSEUS, which are under implementation under the topic HORIZON-CL3-2021-BM-01-03 - Improved border checks for travel facilitation across external borders and improved experiences for both passengers and border authorities' staff, call HORIZON-CL3-2021-BM-01.

ISIG will support the establishment of connections with other sister projects specifically with SAFE-CITIES – riSk – based Approach For the protection of public spaces in European CITIES on call HORIZON-CL3-2021-FTC01-07 and with I-SEAMORE – INTEGRATED SURVEILLANCE ECOSYSTEM FOR EUROPEAN AUTHORITIES RESPONSIBLE FOR MARITIME OPERATIONS LEVERAGED BY RELIABLE AND ENHANCED AERIAL SUPPORT on call HORIZON-CL3-2021-BM-01-01.

RAPI will participate as a guest speaker for the partner's monthly online meeting called Peday. PEN-CP, the Pan-European Network of Customs Practitioners an EU Horizon 2020 funded Customs security practitioner project can be a great clustering opportunity.

UIC is an active member of the [CERIS](#) community which, among others, aims to promote European integrated border management, including border control, risk analysis, information sharing, inter-agency cooperation, use of state-of-the-art technology, and more. The participation of the BM meetings may support future clustering activities.

RBP will perform clustering activities with FLEXICROSS project, an EU-funded initiative with the aim to offer a flexible and improved border experience for passengers and authorities.

4.7.1 Clustering plan of actions

The strategy of collaboration with other EU funded projects is based on more directions:

- To target the projects that are funded under same call and topic as ODYSSEUS: HORIZON-CL3-2021-BM-01-03 - Improved border checks for travel facilitation across external borders and improved experiences for both passengers and border authorities' staff.
- To target other similar EU-funded projects (e.g., projects funded under the H2020-SEC-2016-2017-2).
- To establish synergies with EU agencies with the vision to exchange knowledge and share experiences cultivated during the project's lifespan, as Frontex.

The actions planned for building synergies are summarised in the following Table:

Table 4: Clustering actions

No.	Action	Targeted entity	Description
1	Joining Project Clusters on Border Management	H2020 BES Cluster Pan-European Network of Customs Practitioners	ODYSSEUS joined H2020 BES Cluster since March 2023. A presentation of ODYSSEUS was done by the Project Manager on the PEN-Day on 15 January 2024.
2	Participation in events further organised by EU and EU related organisations, i.e. Frontex	Projects to Policy Seminar 2023 Frontex Workshop December 2023	Project Coordinator participated and represented the project in both events.
3	Creation of synergy links with other projects under Border Management and Security calls	I-SEAMORE, FLEXI-cross, MELCHIOR, BORDER UAS, BAG-INTEL, EURMARS, IFLOWS, PARSEC.	Project Coordinator and Dissemination Manager initiated discussions and established cooperation with I-SEAMORE, FLEXI-cross, MELCHIOR, BORDER UAS, BAG-

No.	Action	Targeted entity	Description
			INTEL until 31 May 2024. Initiation of discussions with EURMARS, IFLOWS, PARSEC will follow in the second half of 2024.
4	Participation in synergy workshops organised by other projects	I-SEAMORE, FLEXI-cross, Border UAS and other	The Project Coordinator alongside with the Dissemination Manager, the Innovation Manager the Ethics Advisor and technical partners participated in three such events until 31 May 2024
5	Organization of Synergy workshops with sister projects	Technical Workshop Ethical Workshop	October 2024 November 2024
6	Horizon Results Booster enrolment	HRB platform	Enrolment done on 21 May 2024, alongside with project Flexi-Cross and TENSOR in one working group
7	Articles or white papers	journals	ongoing

1. Joining Project Clusters on Border Management-this is one of the action taken to target liaisons with projects funded under calls i.e. HORIZON-CL3-2021-BM-01-03 or H2020-SEC-2016-2017-2. ODYSSEUS joined H2020 BES Cluster in March 2023: [BES Cluster – Meticos-Project](#).

On 15 January 2024, ODYSSEUS made a presentation at the PEN-Day in front of several members of European Border Customs Authorities, initiating discussions to establish synergies with PEN-CP project: [Innovation for Customs Administrations | PEN-CP Project](#). Such actions will continue to find and raise awareness and interest for the project.

2. Participation in events further organised by EU and EU related organisations, i.e. Frontex. So far ODYSSEUS participated in Projects to Policy Conference organised by CERIS in 14-15 June 2023 and in a workshop organised by Frontex on 14 December 2023. Both meetings served to raise awareness of the innovation and on the solutions offered by the project and also served for initiating cooperation with other projects and with Frontex.
3. Creation of synergy links with other projects under Border Management and Security calls.

At the end of May 2024 (M17), ODYSSEUS established synergies with the following projects:

- a. BAG-INTEL: [Bag-Intel](#)
- b. BorderUAS: [Border UAS – Border Unmanned Aerial System](#)
- c. I-SEAMORE: [I-SEAMORE – Integrated surveillance ecosystem \(iseamore-project.eu\)](#)
- d. Flexi-cross: [Home - FLEXI-Cross \(flexicross-project.eu\)](#)
- e. MELCHIOR: [MELCHIOR – Melchior Project \(melchior-project.eu\)](#)

Table 5: Sister projects

Project	Short description
	An intelligent system to improve customs control of passenger baggage
	Unmanned Aerial Systems to monitor and secure borders
	Maritime surveillance operations resorting to aerial and water surface support?
	Flexible and adaptive solutions for efficient cross-border trade facilitation
	Enhance infrasound technology in border controls in airports, seaports and land borders

4. Participation in synergy workshops organised by other projects:

The Project Coordinator alongside with the Dissemination Manager, the Innovation Manager, the Ethics Advisor and technical partners participated in three such events until 31 May 2024:

- a. Synergy workshop with sister projects- organised by I-SEAMORE on 12 January 2024: [ODYSSEUS participation at the Synergy Workshop by I-SEAMORE - Odysseus Project](#)
 - b. FCT and BM Synergy Workshop Organised by TENSOR: <https://odysseusproject.eu/odysseus-project-at-fct-and-bm-synergy-workshop>
 - c. Border UAS final conference: [\(21\) ODYSSEUS project: Posts | LinkedIn](#)
5. Organisation of Synergy workshops with sister projects: two synergy workshops are planned – a Technical one in October 2024 and an Ethical one in November 2024. At least one synergy workshop will be held in 2025.
 6. Horizon Results Booster enrolment- Enrolment on the HRB platform was done on 21 May 2024, alongside projects Flexi-Cross and TENSOR in a common working group.
 7. Articles or white papers- will be written together with sister projects.

Overall, clustering with other projects is an integral part of ODYSSEUS dissemination and communication strategy. It enables us to leverage collective knowledge, resources, and networks, amplifying our impact, and fostering a collaborative ecosystem that drives positive change in our sector.

4.8 TARGET AUDIENCE - UPDATED

The identification of target audiences is a critical prerequisite for efficient dissemination results. ODYSSEUS target audiences have been chosen after discussion with the consortium and include citizens (as travellers, employees, security officers, custom operators, security practitioners) border guard authorities, law-enforcement agents, researchers, and S/W engineers working at academia and industry, policy makers and regulators, standardisation organisations at EU and global level, public administration and authorities at local and EU level, and mobile device's manufacturers.

ODYSSEUS target audiences include:

1. Citizens: This group consists of individuals who are either travellers, employees in the transportation sector, security officers, customs operators, or security practitioners. By targeting this audience, ODYSSEUS aims to raise awareness among those directly impacted by border security measures. Providing user-friendly information about ODYSSEUS technologies and how they aim to improve their travel experience, such as reducing wait times at borders and enhancing security through public service announcements, social media, and informational leaflets ensures widespread understanding among diverse demographics.

2. **Border Guard Authorities and Law Enforcement Agents:** This category contains staff responsible for checking the vehicles, goods and the identity information of the travellers crossing the borders. The ODYSSEUS technologies empower Border Authorities and LEAs with innovative tools that assist in conducting an automated and high secure border control while reducing their workload. This group is essential for ODYSSEUS pilot use cases as they will be actively engaged in the real-life scenarios of ODYSSEUS pilots and validate the attempt to upscale their operational capabilities as early adopters of the proposed solution the project offers. The information shared with this type of audience gives emphasis on the efficiency and security benefits of ODYSSEUS technologies in border control operations and how these technologies update their workflow and enhance their ability to detect potential threats.
3. **Researchers and Software Engineers:** Academia and industry professionals working in the fields of research and software engineering form another crucial audience. In this group people have the expertise to evaluate the effectiveness of the existing border management and to develop and suggest pioneering methods to improve border monitoring. By targeting this group, ODYSSEUS aims to foster collaboration, share valuable insights, and contribute to advancements in border security technologies and methodologies. Presenting detailed technical specifications and data about the ODYSSEUS technologies is the most effective way to address to this type of audience to facilitate evaluation and feedback ultimately leading to more robust and efficient solutions.
4. **Policy Makers and Regulators:** Engaging with policy makers and regulators is essential to ensure that ODYSSEUS aligns with the broader policy landscape. Members of this group form and distribute a set of rules and guidelines to EU nations to monitor and regulate the transportation of people and goods across land, air, and sea borders. By sharing the project findings and recommendations, the ODYSSEUS consortium seeks to influence policy decisions and contribute to the development of effective border management frameworks. The approach of this group is to highlight the alignment of ODYSSEUS with current policies and regulations and the way the project contributes to the achievement of common policy goals. By offering evidence-based insights and proposals for policy formulation, ODYSSEUS ensures sure it stays significant and influential in the regulatory framework.
5. **Standardisation Organisations:** This audience defines and establishes border management standards to secure and facilitate the movement of people and goods across EU borders. Engaging with standardisation organisations allows ODYSSEUS to contribute to the development of harmonised standards and best practices. By exchanging data and insights from the ODYSSEUS pilots to guide industry-wide standard setting, this target group is approached.

6. **Public Administration and Authorities:** This group is directly involved in the management of borders. Engaging with public administration and authorities at the local and EU levels is vital for fostering collaboration, ensuring alignment with regulatory frameworks, and promoting the adoption of innovative border management solutions. Fostering discussion and teamwork between different levels of administration promotes a unified approach to border management and providing practical guidance on integrating ODYSSEUS technologies into current, ensuring smooth implementation and adoption.
7. **Mobile Device Manufacturers:** The use of mobile devices as passports and means of passenger identification is a groundbreaking shift that can make travel for passengers a lot easier and creates a high demand in the market. By communicating the solutions of the project, the ODYSSEUS consortium aims to draw manufacturers to address security considerations and explore opportunities for collaboration in enhancing the security of mobile devices within the border security context. ODYSSEUS can attract manufacturers to explore the potential of collaboration by highlighting the benefits and security characteristics of integration, such as improved passenger convenience and security. To visually represent the different categories of audiences that ODYSSEUS addresses, we have created an infographic (Figure 17) within the relevant section of our website. This infographic provides a clear and concise overview of the various target audiences and their involvement in the project. By targeting these diverse audiences and tailoring our dissemination efforts accordingly, we aim to maximize the impact and reach of the ODYSSEUS project, ensuring that our research, findings, and innovations benefit the relevant stakeholders and contribute to advancements in the field of border security.

Figure 17: ODYSSEUS Target Audiences

4.9 INDICATORS OF SUCCESSFUL DISSEMINATION - UPDATED

At some point, success must be measured. KPI is measurable indicator of performance over time in order to understand if the dissemination actions are performing well or not and act accordingly. For that reason, the following key performance indicators (Table 6) will be used to assess the effectiveness of the aforementioned dissemination efforts and ODYSSEUS's outreach to the targeted audiences. Physical measures indicators such as the ODYSSEUS leaflets are easy to determine as they are something that can be calculated and recorded in reporting dissemination activities. Regarding digital measures a variety of online tools are available. To get valuable information to understand the performance of the ODYSSEUS website ACC has installed the web analytics service of Google (Google analytics) that tracks, analyses, and reports on website activity including traffic, visitor source, and user clicks. Google analytics offers all the necessary tools to understand the website visitor journey and optimize the website. On the other hand, the ODYSSEUS Social media accounts have their own insights that help acknowledge which are the more interesting posts related to the ODYSSEUS, what is the best day or time for the audience to engage with posts about ODYSSEUS and the level of engagement of the content selected to be posted overall. The newsletter has been crafted using the Mailchimp platform, providing valuable insights into key metrics such as open rates (indicating the number of recipients who accessed the newsletter), click-through rates (reflecting the

audience's engagement with embedded links), and the geographic distribution of recipients. Mailchimp's dashboard offers a comprehensive overview of newsletter performance through which ACC can make data-driven decisions to enhance future campaigns, leading to improved engagement and outcomes.

Table 6: ODYSSEUS Communication Key Performance Indicators

Measure	Key Performance Indicator	Target	Means of verification
Brochures	Number of e-brochures distributed	>200 per year	Dissemination reporting activities
Posters	Number of posters distributed	2 in total	Dissemination reporting activities
High-level materials for policy makers	Number of sets	>1 per year	Dissemination reporting activities
Website	Number of unique visitors	> 1000 visitors/year	Google analytics
Social networks	Number of followers in: Twitter, LinkedIn number of views: YouTube	>200, >600 >300	Active profiles on such networks via regular posting & monitoring
Workshops	Number of workshops and participants	3 workshops / 100 participants/event	Attendance proofs (e.g., photos, presentations, videos, interviews)
Videos	Number of videos published on the project's YouTube channel and average number of views	2 videos and > 1000 views per video	Videos published via the YouTube channel of the project
Publications	Number of peer-reviewed papers/articles	>10 until the end of the project	Papers/articles published in proceedings & online in premium quality

Measure	Key Performance Indicator	Target	Means of verification
			conferences and journals

5 THE ODYSSEUS STAKEHOLDER COMMUNITY

5.1 INTRODUCTION

One of the primary objectives of the ODYSSEUS project is to actively engage and collaborate with a wide range of stakeholders to ensure the successful implementation and uptake of project outcomes. To achieve this, an important initial step was the comprehensive mapping of the ODYSSEUS Stakeholder Community. This process aimed to identify and analyse the diverse groups and individuals who have a vested interest or play a crucial role in the field of border management. Understanding the composition and actions of the stakeholder community is one of the key factors of successful stakeholder engagement. A comprehensive mapping study will be carried out in the early stages of the project to identify and categorize the main stakeholders important to the project's aims and outcomes. This section summarizes the mapping process's findings and insights, emphasising the diversity and significance of the ODYSSEUS stakeholder community.

5.2 DEVELOPMENT OF STAKEHOLDER COMMUNITY

Stakeholders are an essential component to consider when designing dissemination and communication plans because they will become a key audience once the project begins, not only for disseminating ODYSSEUS's activities but also for promoting the market adoption of its outcomes making concrete use of the results.

With the purpose to improve the community receptivity and participation from the beginning of the project and obtain input from the project's early stages, ODYSSEUS dissemination initiatives will focus on groups that are directly interested in and affected by our project outputs.

The mapping exercise began with an extensive literature review and consultation with project partners to identify the key stakeholders associated with border management. This initial research provided valuable insights into the various sectors, organisations, and individuals involved in border security, transportation, logistics, law enforcement, policymaking, academia, and technology development.

Using this information as a foundation, a systematic approach was employed to identify and categorise stakeholders based on their relevance, influence, and potential impact on the ODYSSEUS project. The identified stakeholders will then be classified into distinct categories to facilitate a comprehensive understanding of their roles and interests.

Each target group will be reached through a different channel thus it needs the appropriate dissemination strategy (Table 7).

The mapping of the ODYSSEUS Stakeholder Community will provide valuable insights into the diverse landscape of actors involved in border management. It will enable the project consortium to develop targeted communication and engagement strategies tailored to the specific needs and interests of different stakeholder groups.

The findings from this mapping exercise will serve as a foundation for the subsequent stages of stakeholder engagement and collaboration throughout the project's lifecycle.

Table 7: ODYSSEUS Stakeholder Engagement

Target audience	Communication Strategy channels
Citizens and Public (Border) authorities	Workshops and Training activities
Research Community Special Issues organization	Journals and workshops
Industrial and Business world	E-marketing campaigns, news, mailing lists, e-magazines, articles, online press, and on-site promotions. Exhibitions and specialized events. Public Relation, word of mouth, assessment written by independent reviewers.
General Public	Advertising in newspapers and magazines, flyers and periodicals, articles/papers for publication, bloggers, maximum visibility on the internet via high ranking to search engines and strong social media presence.

5.3 INVITATION TO JOIN THE COMMUNITY

Furthermore, as part of our ongoing efforts to engage stakeholders, we are actively preparing for sharing with all partners an invitation template. This activity aims to extend invitations to the identified stakeholders, inviting them to actively participate and become part of the ODYSSEUS Stakeholder Community.

Through this invitation, we seek to foster a sense of collaboration among stakeholders, inviting them to contribute their expertise, insights, and perspectives to the project. By joining the ODYSSEUS Community, stakeholders will have the opportunity to stay informed about project developments, participate in discussions, provide feedback, and contribute to the successful implementation and uptake of project outcomes.

The invitation will provide clear instructions on how stakeholders can actively engage with the project, access project resources, and contribute to the ongoing dialogue and collaboration.

By extending invitations to join the community, we are confident that we will attract a wide range of stakeholders who share our vision and commitment to enhancing border management, facilitating smooth and secure transport, and promoting international cooperation. Their active participation and contributions will enrich the project's outcomes and ensure that the ODYSSEUS project remains responsive to the needs and aspirations of the broader stakeholder community.

As we move forward, we will continue to actively engage with stakeholders, seeking their input and feedback, and nurturing a collaborative environment conducive to open dialogue and mutual learning.

6 ODYSSEUS STANDARDISATION ACTIVITIES - UPDATED

This section reports on the activities of Task 6.5 – Impact on Operational Standards and Standardisation Activities, which started at M13, and on the preliminary results achieved at M17. The final report will be provided at M36, within the framework of Deliverable D6.3 Dissemination, Communication, Exploitation and Stakeholders Engagement Report - final.

Task 6.5 pursues two main objectives:

1. Provide recommendation to Border Guards Authorities and Law Enforcement Agencies (LEAs) at national and EU level for the improvement of operational processes, both during evidence extraction and collection and investigation procedures.
2. Develop the ODYSSEUS Standardisation Strategy, by mapping and analysing the key innovation and standardisation potential of the project, through a co-production approach that will actively engage both technical partners and end-users.

The standardisation activities (Task 6.5) and related results (standardisable and exploitable outputs, as well as overall recommendations) will be promoted also beyond the consortium, in synergy with dissemination and communication activities (Task 6.1).

In this regard, under the coordination of the Standardisation Manager (THALES), the Standardisation Strategy will identify suitable opportunities and initiatives for promoting and raising awareness on the ODYSSEUS overall standardisation outputs.

6.1 BACKGROUND

6.1.1 EU Strategy on Standardisation¹

The European Commission introduced its new standardisation strategy on 2 February 2022, as part of the wider initiative: 'Updating the 2020 New Industrial Strategy: Building a stronger Single Market for Europe's recovery'. This approach is expected to enhance European leadership in setting global standards and transform standardisation into a major driver of competitiveness and resilience. It also targets green and digital transitions by embedding democratic values in technological applications.

¹ https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/single-market/european-standards/standardisation-policy/standardisation-strategy_en

This strategy highlights the importance of standards in addressing current industrial challenges within the Single Market and globally. It takes a holistic approach, with various key actions aimed at making standardisation a major driver of European competitiveness and resilience while ensuring that Europe continues to lead in world standards.

The Strategy defines 5 key sets of actions:

1. **Priority setting and speed:** a High-Level Forum on European Standardisation will be established. Among other things, this forum will help predict future standardisation priorities, guide standardisation policy-making process, define annual priority areas or themes in relation to standards development and identify future needs for further standardisation. In addition, it will consider how academia can be more linked to research activities related with standardisation. Moreover, an EU Excellence Hub on Standards will support the Chief Standardisation Officer in strengthening internal cooperation and expertise on standardisation.
2. **Good Governance:** to improve governance in the European standardisation system, the Commission proposes amendments to the regulation on standardisation. This aims to promote inclusiveness and integrated governance, urging European standardisation organisations (ESOs) to modernize their governance to better support EU policy and legislation.
3. **European Leadership in Global Standards:** the Commission, through the High-Level Forum, will create a new mechanism for sharing information, coordinating, and strengthening the European approach to international standardisation with EU countries and national standardisation bodies.
4. **Support Innovation:** The Commission has launched a 'standardisation booster' to create a stronger ecosystem between research and innovation (R&I) and standards. This initiative connects Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe beneficiaries with standardisation experts. Additionally, the Commission will develop a code of practice for researchers to strengthen the integration of standardisation with research and innovation within the European Research Area.
5. **Education and Skills:** To promote academic awareness and prepare future standardisation experts, the Commission will organize EU University Days on standards. This initiative aims to share best practices and anticipate the future demand for expertise in standardisation.

The ODYSSEUS project, in line with strategic priorities of the Commission, within the framework of Task 6.5, will develop a Standardisation Strategy, ultimately contributing to make standardisation a key driver of European industrial strength and sustainable development

6.1.2 Digital Document Standardisation Activities

International travel is back to its growth pass after being significantly impacted by the COVID-19 pandemic. IATA, the International Air Transport Association, predicts that air passenger numbers will recover by 2024 [1]. The total number of worldwide air travellers is expected to exceed 4 billion, which is a three percent increase over 2019. For Europe alone (to/from/within), the forecast is for a five

percent increase over 2019. In the long run, IATA forecasts 7.2 billion air travellers by 2035 according their 20-year forecast dating from 2016.

While these number represent just air travel, it can be safely assumed that land and sea-based travel will have fully recovered by 2024 as well and will continue to grow. There is, though, not such forecast available as for air travel.

The growth of international traveller numbers asks for procedures for border crossing that at the same time satisfy the travellers expectations for a swift and seamless border crossing as well as the border guard authorities' duty to keep up security and protect the borders.

Border-crossing procedures at air borders are constantly assessed and optimized for efficiency and security. The procedures are well understood and largely harmonized and standardized, which is a necessary basis not only for a flawless travel experience but also for the industry to come up with solutions that enable such swift yet secure travel facilitation. ODYSSEUS leverages knowledge and experiences from air borders while keeping focus on and proposing solutions for crossing land and sea borders in a secure and seamless manner.

Traveller identification in international travel is regulated by the International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO), a specialized agency of the United Nations (UN). ICAO's role is that of a standards-setting organization for travel related matters (an example is Doc.9303 standardizing Machine-Readable Travel Documents). The 193 ICAO member states – which includes all EU member states – adopt ICAO's mandatory regulations and standards.

ICAO hence is a first main standards setting body that is monitored and which will be targeted to share and discuss the results from the ODYSSEUS project. The relevant entity of ICAO is its New Technology Working Group (NTWG) that is preparing and revising as necessary the standards in the Traveller Identification Program. NTWG does delegate the actual standards development to ISO, the International Standards Organization, here namely to JTC1 SC17 WG3 ('Working Group 3' or WG3). Working Group 3 is itself liaising with other relevant working groups such all other working groups within SC17 'Cards and security devices for personal identification', including WG10 for driving and mobile driving licenses, and other sub-committees including SC27 on Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection, and SC37 on Biometrics.

In a European context, the Schengen Area guarantees border-free movement for EU citizens as well as for non-EU national residents in a Schengen Country or visiting a Schengen Country as tourists, as exchange students or for business purposes. The Schengen provisions abolish checks at internal borders, while providing a uniform set of rules for controls at the Schengen external borders. Hence, ODYSSEUS findings will primarily be useful for the Schengen External Borders even though Schengen Countries may temporarily reintroduce border controls at internal borders and could then as well benefit from the results of ODYSSEUS.

The European Union has enacted rules and regulations that govern the movement of persons across Schengen External borders (Schengen Border Code). The relevant entity preparing rules and regulations is the European Commission's

Directorate-General for Migration and Home Affairs (DG HOME). Frontex, the European Border and Coast Guard Agency, on the other hand defines and coordinates operational border control aspects among Schengen Countries, is e.g., responsible for the False and Authentic Documents Online (FADO) system and is generally involved in Border Security Research. Hence, Frontex is identified as an important entity to review results with.

THALES is a regular participant in NTWG activities and is a member in various ISO working groups. THALES will use its involvement in standards bodies as well as its connections to the European Commission and Frontex to bring in ODYSSEUS findings for review and discussion and disseminate final results.

6.2 TOWARDS THE DEFINITION OF THE ODYSSEUS STANDARDISATION STRATEGY

The definition and implementation of the ODYSSEUS Standardisation Strategy is a structured process, started at M13 (January 2024), and foresees three main phases:

Figure 18: Phases towards the definition of ODYSSEUS Standardisation Strategy

The following paragraphs provide a description of each phase.

6.2.1 Phase 1: Preparation and preliminary mapping (M13 – M18)

Within the preliminary phase (M13-M18) the following actions are foreseen and have been implemented:

1. Kick-off

Task 6.5 officially kicked off on February 7th, 2024, within the periodic WP6 meeting.

2. Establishment of the Standardisation Task force

To guarantee the maximum synergy between tasks T6.1 and T6.5, a dedicated work group has been established with representatives of partners involved (mainly ACC, ISIG and THALES). The task force will meet regularly (at least 1 per month, starting with M13) so to better coordinate and potentially co-produce the Standardisation Strategy. Moreover, Task force representatives will be invited to the standardisation workshops and overall co-production process, envisaged by task 6.5 for the purpose of mapping and analysing ODYSSEUS standardisation potential.

3. Preliminary mapping and analysis

In collaboration with the Standardisation Task Force, a standardisation on-line survey (available at this [link](#)) has been developed to understand the standardisation potential of the project, and map relevant standardisation opportunities, bodies and forums, as a baseline for the development of the ODYSSEUS standardisation strategy. The survey was launched on April 26th, 2024. The survey template is presented in Annex 3: ODYSSEUS Standardisation Survey and Preliminary results in Section 6.3.1 (ODYSSEUS Standardisation Survey).

6.2.2 Phase 2: Co-production and development (M19-M24)

The second phase foresees the following steps:

1. Engagement of project partners and end-users

In the second half of 2024, ODYSSEUS project partners and end-users will be involved in participatory workshops to validate the results of Phase 1, identify the project's major standardisation potential and co-define the Standardisation Action Plan, to be implemented in the last year of ODYSSEUS.

2. Analysis of ODYSSEUS innovation and standardisation potential

Starting from the results of preliminary analysis performed in Phase 1, a detailed analysis of project's innovations for the identification of standardisation opportunities will be conducted. Standardisation requirements will be defined.

3. Definition of the Action Plan

The Action Plan for the implementation of the ODYSSEUS Standardisation Strategy will be drafted, to submit the contributions to relevant standardisation forums and bodies (indicatively ICAO 9303, ISO18013, ISOSC17, OpenID Foundation, FIDO Alliance, ENISA, Doc 9303, etc.). The Action Plan will include monitoring indicators and indications on internal procedures for submission.

6.2.3 Phase 3: Action Plan implementation and monitoring (M25-M36)

1. Implementation

In the last year of project implementation, the Standardisation Action Plan will be implemented and contributions to relevant standardisation bodies and forums submitted².

2. Monitoring and Evaluation

The implementation of the Action Plan will be subject to periodic monitoring and a final evaluation.

3. Reporting

All the outcomes of Task 6.5 will be reported in D6.3, due at M36.

6.3 PRELIMINARY RESULTS AND OUTCOMES

6.3.1 ODYSSEUS Standardisation Survey

6.3.1.1 Structure

The ODYSSEUS Standardisation Strategy is structured into nine sections:

1. **Identification of respondents:** to collect information on respondents' contact details and organisations.
2. **Innovations identification:** to identify key ODYSSEUS innovations and their potential for standardisation.
3. **Standardisation objectives:** to define potential standardisation objectives do of ODYSSEUS.
4. **Identification of standardisation opportunities:** to map relevant standards, both existing and under development.
5. **Identification of forums and bodies:** for the definition of criteria for selecting relevant standardisation forums and bodies for the submission of contributions and identification of specific forums and bodies.
6. **Partners involvement:** to define the potential support of partners in the implementation of ODYSSEUS Standardisation Strategy.
7. **End-user Engagement/Identification of stakeholders:** to define potential interaction with external stakeholders and end-users.
8. **Submission plan:** to define a time plan for submission.
9. **Monitoring and evaluation:** to define indicators and criteria for monitoring and evaluation ODYSSEUS standardisation efforts.

6.3.1.2 Data collection

The online survey, hosted on the SurveyMonkey platform (EU based), was launched on April 26th, 2024, and data collection was closed on May 30th, 2024.

² In 2024, two applications to present ODYSSEUS to relevant standardisation groups are planned – ref. Section 6.3.2.

Eight partners, out of fourteen, participated to the survey. In order to collect more answers and draft a comprehensive overview of ODYSSEUS standardisation potential, a second round of data collection will be launched in June 2024.

Preliminary results are presented in the section below.

6.3.1.3 Preliminary Results

The following table reports on: the key innovations of ODYSSEUS, their alignment with existing standards, specific standardisation objectives, existing relevant standards, and standards under development.

Table 8: ODYSSEUS standardisation potential

Key innovations	Alignment with existing standards or standardisation efforts	Standardisation objective	Existing standards/regulations	relevant Standards development under
Digital and Virtual Passport	Strong alignment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide feedback on DTC implementation on mobile devices and usability. • Provide feedback on integration with legacy Border Control systems. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ICAO Digital Travel Credentials (DTC) Virtual Component Data Structure and PKI Mechanisms. • ICAO Doc 9303 Machine Readable Travel Documents.³ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ICAO Digital Travel Credentials (DTC) Physical Component and Protocols.
UAV-assisted, Non-Obtrusive and Safe X-Ray Technologies for Vehicle Scanning	Strong alignment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contribution to/provide feedback on safety Standards. • Contribution to/provide feedback on ethical and data protection standards/principles. • Contribution to/provide feedback on Data Interoperability, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ISO/IEC 27001 - Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection — Information security management systems — Requirements.⁴ • ISO 9011:2015 - Quality management systems — Requirements.⁵ 	

³ <https://www.iso.org/standard/72891.html>

⁴ <https://www.iso.org/standard/27001>

⁵ <https://www.iso.org/standard/62085.html>

Key innovations	Alignment with existing standards or standardisation efforts	Standardisation objective	Existing standards/regulations relevant	Standards development under
		Regulatory Compliance, Quality Assurance, Environmental Impact, Integration with Existing Infrastructure.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ISO 14001:2015 - Environmental management systems — Requirements with guidance for use.⁶ • ISO/TC 20/SC - Aircraft and space vehicles.⁷ • "Schengen catalogue recommendations and best practices - data protection" and Handbook on European data protection law. • Regulation (EU) 2018/1725 of the European parliament and of the Council of 23 October 2018 on the protection of natural 	

⁶ <https://www.iso.org/standard/60857.html>

⁷ <https://www.iso.org/committee/46484.html>

Key innovations	Alignment with existing standards or standardisation efforts	Standardisation objective	Existing standards/regulations relevant	Standards development under
			<p>persons with regard to the processing of personal data by the Union institutions, bodies, offices and agencies and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Regulation (EC) No 45/2001 and Decision No 1247/2002/EC.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • REGULATION (EU) 2016/679 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL from April 27, 2016, on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data and repeal of Directive 95/46/EC. 	
Seamless Identity	Strong alignment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contribution to/provide feedback on 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ICAO/ • ISO/IEC 19794-5 compliance - specifies 	

Key innovations	Alignment with existing standards or standardisation efforts	Standardisation objective	Existing standards/regulations	relevant Standards development under
Verification in Border Crossing Scenarios		aspects linked to efficiency and Cost Reduction. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contribution on provide with quality standards 	scene, photographic, digitization and format requirements for images of faces to be used in the context of both human verification and computer automated recognition.	
Multi-modal fusion and AI-based decision support system	Strong alignment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contribution to/provide feedback on quality decision making standards. Contribution to/provide feedback on trustworthy AI principles. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ISO/IEC 23894:2023 - Information technology — Artificial intelligence — Guidance on risk management.⁸ ISO/IEC TR 24028:2020 - Information technology — Artificial intelligence — Overview of 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ISO/IEC AWI TS 17847 - Information technology — Artificial intelligence — Verification and validation analysis of AI systems.¹² ISO/IEC AWI TR 20226 - Information technology — Artificial intelligence —

⁸ <https://www.iso.org/standard/77304.html?browse=tc>

¹² <https://www.iso.org/standard/85072.html?browse=tc>

Key innovations	Alignment with existing standards or standardisation efforts	Standardisation objective	Existing standards/regulations relevant	Standards development under
			trustworthiness in artificial intelligence. ⁹ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <li data-bbox="1272 491 1637 715">• ISO/IEC TR 24027:2021 - Information technology — Artificial intelligence (AI) — Bias in AI systems and AI aided decision making.¹⁰ <li data-bbox="1272 719 1637 911">• ISO/IEC TR 24368:2022 - Information technology — Artificial intelligence — Overview of ethical and societal concerns¹¹ 	Environmental sustainability aspects of AI systems. ¹³ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <li data-bbox="1709 523 2074 778">• ISO/IEC AWI TS 22443 - Information technology — Artificial intelligence — Guidance on addressing societal concerns and ethical considerations.¹⁴ <li data-bbox="1709 783 2074 941">• ISO/IEC AWI 42105 - Information technology — Artificial intelligence — Guidance for human

⁹ <https://www.iso.org/standard/77608.html?browse=tc>

¹⁰ <https://www.iso.org/standard/77607.html?browse=tc>

¹¹ <https://www.iso.org/standard/78507.html?browse=tc>

¹³ <https://www.iso.org/standard/86177.html>

¹⁴ <https://www.iso.org/standard/87119.html?browse=tc>

Key innovations	Alignment with existing standards or standardisation efforts	Standardisation objective	Existing standards/regulations relevant	Standards development under
				oversight of AI systems ¹⁵ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <li data-bbox="1709 491 2074 778">• ISO/IEC AWI TR 42106 - Information technology — Artificial intelligence — Overview of differentiated benchmarking of AI system quality characteristics.¹⁶ <li data-bbox="1709 786 2074 975">• ISO/IEC CD 42005 - Information technology — Artificial intelligence — AI system impact assessment.¹⁷

¹⁵ <https://www.iso.org/standard/86902.html?browse=tc>

¹⁶ <https://www.iso.org/standard/86903.html?browse=tc>

¹⁷ <https://www.iso.org/standard/44545.html?browse=tc>

Key innovations	Alignment with existing standards or standardisation efforts	Standardisation objective	Existing standards/regulations	relevant Standards under development
Behavioural Authentication Models	Moderate alignment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contribution to/provide feedback on anonymization and encryption to ensure compliance with global privacy regulations and create common interfaces and data exchange protocols for seamless integration with existing authentication systems and IT infrastructure - Designing APIs and data formats that are compatible with 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ISO/IEC 27001 - Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection — Information security management systems — Requirements.¹⁸ ISO/IEC 23894:2023 - Information technology — Artificial intelligence — Guidance on risk management.¹⁹ ISO/IEC TR 24028:2020 - Information technology — Artificial intelligence — Overview of 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ISO/IEC AWI TS 17847 - Information technology — Artificial intelligence — Verification and validation analysis of AI systems.²³ ISO/IEC AWI TR 20226 - Information technology — Artificial intelligence — Environmental sustainability aspects of AI systems.²⁴ ISO/IEC AWI TS 22443 - Information technology — Artificial intelligence —

¹⁸ <https://www.iso.org/standard/27001>

¹⁹ <https://www.iso.org/standard/77304.html?browse=tc>

²³ <https://www.iso.org/standard/85072.html?browse=tc>

²⁴ <https://www.iso.org/standard/86177.html>

Key innovations	Alignment with existing standards or standardisation efforts	Standardisation objective	Existing standards/regulations relevant	Standards development under
		multiple platforms and devices. • Contribution to/provide feedback on ethical and trustworthy AI principles.	trustworthiness in artificial intelligence. ²⁰ • ISO/IEC TR 24027:2021 - Information technology — Artificial intelligence (AI) — Bias in AI systems and AI aided decision making. ²¹ • ISO/IEC TR 24368:2022 - Information technology — Artificial intelligence — Overview of ethical and societal concerns. ²²	Guidance on addressing societal concerns and ethical considerations. ²⁵ • ISO/IEC AWI 42105 - Information technology — Artificial intelligence — Guidance for human oversight of AI systems. ²⁶ • ISO/IEC AWI TR 42106 - Information technology — Artificial intelligence — Overview of differentiated

²⁰ <https://www.iso.org/standard/77608.html?browse=tc>

²¹ <https://www.iso.org/standard/77607.html?browse=tc>

²² <https://www.iso.org/standard/78507.html?browse=tc>

²⁵ <https://www.iso.org/standard/87119.html?browse=tc>

²⁶ <https://www.iso.org/standard/86902.html?browse=tc>

Key innovations	Alignment with existing standards or standardisation efforts	Standardisation objective	Existing standards/regulations relevant	Standards development under
				benchmarking of AI system quality characteristics. ²⁷ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ISO/IEC CD 42005 - Information technology — Artificial intelligence — AI system impact assessment.²⁸

The main **criteria** suggested by partners for selecting relevant standardisation forums and bodies for submission of contributions are the following:

- Alignment with project objectives.
- Relevance to industry standards.

The main **forums and bodies** that should be prioritised, according to partners, are the following:

- European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA)
- ICAO 9303

²⁷ <https://www.iso.org/standard/86903.html?browse=tc>

²⁸ <https://www.iso.org/standard/44545.html?browse=tc>

- IEEE Standards Association
- ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42 - Artificial intelligence
- National Institute of Standards and Technology
- OpenID Foundation
- European Association for Biometrics

Project partners perceive their **main role** in the standardisation process in terms of:

- Providing technical expertise.
- Contributing to documentation elaboration.
- Participating in standardisation forums.

For what concerns **partners' expertise** in terms of standardisation efforts, partners stressed:

- Technical knowledge.
- Industry experience.
- Regulatory understanding.

End-users should be involved in the standardisation process by:

- Involving end-users in workshops/focus groups.
- Conducting surveys.

6.3.2 Contributions to relevant standardisation groups, bodies and forums

Under the coordination of the Standardisation Manager (THALES), it is planned to present the ODYSSEUS project to two standardisation groups:

1. **Application to present ODYSSEUS to ICAO NTWG (New Technologies Working Group) on topic Future forms of eMRTD and associated systems²⁹.**
The group is interested in all technologies that use eMRTD (electronic passports) and extend its usage or overall improve border crossing processes. It is planned to present an overview of ODYSSEUS project with a presentation of architecture, features and technologies that are used in the project and DTC (Digital Travel Credential) usage within the project, including a description of integration and obstacles the consortium had to overcome when integrating DTC into the ODYSSEUS platform. The application was submitted in May 2024, and if accepted, the presentation will be held in September 2024.
2. **Presentation of the project on CEN TC 224 Plenary meeting in June 2024.**
The CEN TC334 is a group focused on “personal identification and related personal devices with secure elements, systems, operations and privacy in a multi sectorial environment”. The plan is to present a brief overview of the ODYSSEUS project to give context of the DTC usage, with the main focus of the presentation being on the identity management in the ODYSSEUS platform: identity verification, DTC issuance and identity verification done by the platform during the border crossing process.

6.4 NEXT STEPS

At the time of writing (M17), the first Phase of the ODYSSEUS Standardisation Strategy (i.e., Preparation and Preliminary mapping), is about to be concluded. A final analysis of the answers collected through the ODYSSEUS Standardisation Survey will be performed at M19.

The following phases will be implemented as follows:

- Phase 2: Co-production and development → M19-M24
- Phase 3: Action Plan implementation and monitoring → M25-M36

All the results of T6.5 will be reported in Deliverable 6.3 (due in M36).

7 EXPLOITATION - UPDATED

7.1 OVERALL EXPLOITATION STRATEGY-UPDATED

The ODYSSEUS consortium was created to have a balanced and competent partner base with the necessary know how and experience to be able to offer citizens the appropriate tools to cross land and sea borders without intervention in a secure and seamless manner while equipping the border authorities with novel, state-of-the art tools for secure identity verification and unobtrusive luggage checks, eliminating long delays in border areas.

The Seamless Border Cross for Travel Facilitation solution is designed to facilitate the border control process, to ensure identification and control of goods and people using properly Identification equipment as well as an enhancement of the current way of identity verification at the Borders' travellers. Additionally, it is designed to improve the productivity of the Border and coastguards Authorities by combining a set of different technologies provided by ODYSSEUS consortium members.

ODYSSEUS consortium is composed by experts in all related domains of all parts of technologies: technology providers (in AI, X-Rays, UAVs, Identity verification and in cybersecurity), integrators, research institutes, prestigious border authorities (RBP, CDBP, BBA, IGPF MAI), end-users and large industry organisations.

The main goals of the ODYSSEUS exploitation activities are to maximize the project's impact, ensure sustainability, and facilitate the widespread adoption of the developed technology across European borders. In addition, other goals are to explore the market potential of the developments made within the project and to identify the potential of produced results by all project partners, the commercial use of ODYSSEUS technology and identify the opportunities to turn them into commercial offers in targeted markets.

The exploitation strategy of the consortium will be developed in two distinctive manners with differentiated tasks: In a Collective manner (within the consortium) and in an Individual manner (at Partner level). On a Collective manner, there will be a need to coordinate the partners in their various exploitation activities, and to promote these activities in a unified manner among the relevant audiences and assume the responsibility to maximise the visibility of ODYSSEUS project and convey its findings and outputs to the relevant stakeholders relying on their joint outreach capacities. The consortium members will undertake the responsibility of dividing the tasks among themselves based on their areas of expertise, comparative strengths, and respective networks. On an Individual manner, the exploitation strategy has two main directions: the individual partner exploitation and the joint exploitation plans.

Each partner will develop its individual exploitation plan focusing on the Exploitable Assets (EA) of priority for them, documenting how it will contribute to the sustainability of ODYSSEUS services or how it may exploit them directly in

local, regional or international market, considering the IPR strategy of the consortium. A list of exploitable assets is provided in section 7.3, Table 9, along with the market potential of each asset which will be refined during the project implementation.

The individual exploitation plan will consider the following aspects:

- Exploitable Assets and Foreground
- Exploitation Type
- Sector of application
- Timetable for commercial use or any other use
- Patent or other IPR exploitation

While the joint exploitation activities will be co-managed by the consortium, there is a strong motivation among partners to develop high-quality solutions that correspond and fulfil citizens and Border Authority's needs.

The Authorities partners of the project will be mainly responsible for adopting both the proposed project solutions and the developed components, in their infrastructures by promoting the ODYSSEUS Platform solution and validating the solutions developed. The Authorities partners will enhance their capabilities and gather technical knowledge through the integration and the development processes of the ODYSSEUS platform. Results from the project can lead to development of recommendations and guidelines. The project's results (either in the form of scientific publications or in the form of knowledge) will also strengthen the position of the consortium partners in the targeted fields. SMEs will also take advantage of the ODYSSEUS outputs and will acquire significant leverage on the industry domains they specialise in. Newest advances and modules on new AI models combined with various technologies will provide critical assets and expand their market potential and can contribute to the formulation of economically sustainable business plans.

Exploitation strategies will be directed according to the spread of expected outcomes such as: methodologies, tools, models, and guidelines. Each category will have the potential for adoption and commercialisation of results on its own merit. The resulting exploitation directions are shown below and are considered as follows:

- Research, development, and integration activities: Many partners participating in ODYSSEUS will build on and further developing existing research activities in the areas of Artificial Intelligence algorithms, AI-powered behavioural authentication and identity verification, AI multi-modal behavioural analysis, enhance current usage of X-ray technology for advanced scanning usage and Advanced Biometric technologies. As a result, the consortium is expected to increase its knowledge on the project related fields and exploit them.
- More specifically, technology providers that will benefit to commercially exploit the developed research results, the aim is to enhance already commercially available products with new features derived from the ODYSSEUS project outcomes.

- Additionally, the law enforcement agencies can capitalize project results and demonstrate in the medium and long-term benefits of enhancing best practices to the border security.
- Product development: This constitutes the primary exploitation activity within the ODYSSEUS consortium. All participating partners are focused on developing products and solutions that will grant them a competitive edge in their respective market ecosystems. Industrial partners will benefit by exploring and identifying technological challenges, leading to the creation of commercially viable services and products closely related to the project. For exploiting the project results, various approaches will be employed, such as economic analysis regarding the commercial use of the ODYSSEUS platform or integrating individual research findings into the existing platforms or solutions of the individual partners. Consequently, each partner will have the opportunity to design new follow-up projects, initiatives, and market solutions at both national and international levels.
- Standardisation: Industrial partners will expand their networking efforts to include standardisation bodies and other organizations that can impact the adoption of the outcomes and guidelines formulated by this consortium.
- Consulting and specialized services: This exploitation directive will mainly focus on partners keen on transforming the acquired knowledge into consulting and specialized services for their clients. These partners will aim to develop consulting services for the industry, positioning themselves as early adopters, technology providers, or small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs).
- Other: Other forms of exploitation could leverage the project's outcomes, such as knowledge, research findings, methodologies, new services, innovative applications of technologies, algorithms, and more. These outcomes will also be considered when finalizing the project's exploitation plan. Although these outcomes do not qualify as Exploitable Assets because they are not directly exploitable via standard commercial or business routes, we will refer to them as Exploitable Assets (EAs). EAs can still significantly bolster the consortium's exploitation strategy by enabling the development of new solutions, enhancing technological expertise, launching new or improved solutions with additional features, increasing efficiency, addressing issues, and exploring new business models.

The following figure presents a graphic representation of the exploitation strategy:

Figure 19: Exploitation directions of ODYSSEUS Project

The Exploitation/Business Plan specifically aims to include the key elements:

- I. **Market Analysis and Potential Applications**
Odysseus solutions are increasingly relevant across multiple sectors, such as border control, security, finance, and healthcare. The market demand for secure, seamless, and accurate identity verification is growing, driven by global mobility, digital transformation, and the need for enhanced security. This plan identifies key target markets, exploiting the product economically approaching future clients, building up a solid client base, and placing the product in the respective markets
- II. **Commercialization Strategy**
The plan defines a pathway for transitioning the Odysseus Border control solutions from development to commercialization. This includes product offerings for key stakeholders, such as government agencies, private companies, and definition of business plans, for each partner as individual exploitation but also in joint exploitation for the whole platform or for different modules . It also explores licensing agreements, partnerships as joint exploitation agreements, sales models to maximize market penetration and revenue streams. Enrolling the ODYSSEUS platform in Horizon Europe Booster will support the creation of a business plan.

- III. Intellectual Property and Licensing
The exploitation strategy includes the protection of intellectual property (IP) related to the Odysseus solutions developed. Section 7.2 describes how patents, trademarks, and other IP rights will be managed to protect innovations and create licensing opportunities for broader use in the market.
- V. Partnerships and Stakeholder Engagement
To ensure the successful deployment of Odysseus Solutions, strategic partnerships will be cultivated with key players in the context of Odysseus. Stakeholder engagement is critical to gaining trust and meeting the specific needs of each sector, while promoting widespread adoption.
- VI. Risk Management
The plan includes risk mitigation strategies to address potential challenges, such as changes in regulation, public acceptance of Odysseus solutions technologies, and competitive market dynamics. By proactively identifying and addressing these risks, the plan aims to ensure smooth market entry and minimize barriers to adoption.
- VII. Revenue Projections and ROI
A financial forecast is provided to outline expected revenue streams, cost structures, and return on investment (ROI) over time. This ensures that stakeholders can understand the financial benefits of the biometric solutions and make informed decisions regarding investment and further development.

Throughout the project's duration, targeted actions will continuously be implemented to ensure the effective exploitation of its results. The consortium will focus on the following activities:

- Conduct a market analysis to identify target stakeholders and assess the current landscape of competing solutions.
- Each partner will formulate a comprehensive business plan for each Key Exploitable Asset.
- Establish a Joint Exploitation Strategy, developing joint business models aimed at the commercialization of exploitable assets.
- Prepare a Joint Business Plan
- Dissemination and Promotion
- Monitor Progress and Adjust Strategy.

7.1.1 Marketing Exploitation process phases

The overall exploitation framework can be divided into three phases, the “Initial Phase,” the “Trial Phase” and the “Expansion Phase.”

These phases represent major steps towards the establishment of an economically viable product placement and can also be used as success indicators or milestones in the overall exploitation process chain.

During the project lifetime, specific actions that aim to ensure the correct exploitation of the project results will be undertaken.

In more detail, the consortium will perform the following activities.

A. Initial Phase

The Initial Phase marked the initial stage of the project, focusing on establishing the basic ground of the exploitation process. This phase can also be viewed as an orientation period, as it remains uncertain whether the services and products will be suitable or available by the project's conclusion. The Initial Phase concludes once the ODYSSEUS requirements, technologies and platform have been developed by M24 - December 2024. The specifics of the business plans are gathered during this phase, and it is advisable to conduct a follow-up survey later in the project and product implementation.

During the Initial Phase, the following general actions should be implemented:

- Each partner will create an exploitation plan for its own results, including commercial and non-commercial plans.
- The non-commercial exploitation plans to be prepared by consortium members will include a comprehensive list of activities (research and development, publications, training initiatives, standardisation efforts, planning).
- Other results than the initial Exploitable assets should be identified.
- Detailed / final definition of the target groups.
- Listing of potential clients (organizations) in the countries and regions.
- Grouping of the organizations according to identified demands.
- Further development of an ODYSSEUS product specific brand.
- Preparation of basic information material .
- Preparation of templates for contact letters and e-mails.
- Establishing first contacts with the future clients and consortium members.
- Surveys and interviews to identify practical client demands, existing organizational or administrative barriers as well as the existing level of knowledge.
- Development of an ODYSSEUS corporate design and brand.
- Design and ensure the ODYSSEUS Intellectual Property Rights protection strategy implementation.
- Conduct a market analysis with the aim of identifying the targeted stakeholders and the status of competitive solutions.
- The evaluation and creation of the business models, and the development of a business plan.
- Preparation of a suitable, efficient evaluation process.

B. Trial and Evaluation Phase

The Trial and Evaluation Phase begins with the preparation and implementation of the initial pilot training in December 2024-M24 . This phase will extend until the project's conclusion in December 2025-M36, as the ongoing processes of trial, evaluation, and optimization of the training are essential for the product's long-term success in the market. Optimization will occur during the project implementation phase following pilot testing, with the aim of attracting a substantial client base. To improve outreach, effective marketing strategies will be critical.

The most important steps in this phase are:

- Establish a Joint Exploitation Strategy, developing joint business models aimed at the commercialization of exploitable assets.
- Prepare a Joint Business Plan.
- Review the Key Exploitable Assets.
- Monitor Progress and Adjust Strategy.
- Contact potential clients, particularly thematic networks, associations, and multiplier organizations.
- Evaluate and optimize the product in cooperation with future client groups .
- Establish local / regional information campaigns.
- Evaluation, reporting and proposal list for the optimisation of the product.
- Realisation of the product testing/pilot.
- Evaluation of the training and analysis of results.

C. Expansion Phase

The Expansion Phase takes place solely during the post-project period. Its main goals are to consolidate the existing client base, and to broaden that base by introducing the product to new markets. These new markets may extend beyond the current reach of the project partners, indicating that the Expansion Phase is not time-bound and could continue for several years.

In particular, the following actions need to be put into practice:

- Establishing a profit generating product.
- Realization of long-term marketing measures.
- Present the Odysseus product at conferences and fairs.
- Extension of the client base.
- Extension of the geographical scope of product availability.
- Introduction of marketing measures in the new markets.
- Lobbying EU, national, regional and local institutions.

- Ongoing optimization (adaptation) of the product.
- Continuous marketing of the enhanced solutions to ensure they remain always innovative and market responsive.

To illustrate those activities a Timeline for the overall exploitation steps has been created and depicted in figure 20:

Figure 20: Timeline for overall Exploitation strategy

7.2 IPR PROTECTION STRATEGY

Various partners with diverse backgrounds and know-how collaborate within the framework of ODYSSEUS interdisciplinary research and innovation aiming at reaching a goal, i.e. unobtrusive technologies facilitating secure and seamless border crossing. It is of major importance that each partner to appropriately manage and effectively safeguard their knowledge and their expertise being offered to the project. Having what is above-mentioned in mind, it is obvious that the consortium should pay special attention to the critical importance of robust knowledge management practices, conducting and designing the ODYSSEUS' Intellectual Property Rights protection strategy.

To ensure the successful implementation of the IPR protection strategy, the following comprehensive steps are outlined in this deliverable, and will be described in a more detailed way in Deliverable 6.2 Impact Enhancement, Innovation Management, Standardisation Activities and Policy Recommendations on M36:

- The identification of the Background knowledge which each partner brings to the project
- The consideration of the Foreground knowledge, in general, all kind of results possibly exploitable, being generated during the project
- The clarification of possible joint ownership of the exploitable results
- The definition of the type of protection that each partner is willing to take advantage of (e.g. patents, copyrights, trademarks, trade secrets, etc.).

In alignment with the project's workplan, the consortium initiates the implementation of the IPR protection strategy through the following timeline and actions:

- The first round of the required information will be aggregated on M18, through a template/questionnaire, which will be circulated amongst the consortium until M16. This template will be able to monitor all the above-mentioned steps and will be used as an IPR 'living' Registry, meaning that the consortium might access it, and continuously review it on a regular basis, to stay informed of any modifications and updates, as the project moves forward.
- In parallel, worldwide research against the prior art relevant to ODYSSEUS solutions will be undertaken, ensuring their novelty and uniqueness.
- A thorough cost assessment regarding the IPR protection will be carried out, aiming at maximizing the economic benefits, after verifying the proper regions for filing the official patent paperwork.

Finally, a sophisticated approach that establishes a balance between the need to secure the IPR and encourage innovation, while also adhering to the values of transparency and incentivize innovation and cooperation, is necessary to resolve the conflict amongst open science and access rights.

Concluding, the ODYSSEUS project emphasizes on formulating strategic IPR protection measures and efficient knowledge management, while optimizing the impact and sustainability of its research and innovation endeavours.

7.3 KEY EXPLOITABLE ASSETS

Table 9: Key Exploitable assets

Exploitable Asset	Owner	Description	Market Potential
EA1	VISB	Seamless Identity Verification in Border Crossing Scenarios	Identity Verification Market to surpass USD 17.63 billion by 2030 from USD 7.2 billion in 2018 at a CAGR of 15.7% throughout the forecast period, i.e., 2019-30. Key players are Authenteq, IDEMIA, iDenfy, Mitek Systems, Inc., Onfido, TransUnion LLC, Trulioo, Thales Group (Gemalto) and VisionBox. Target customers are commercial, LEAs, Border Authorities, Aviation and Transportation.
EA2	THALES	Digital and Virtual Passport	The global e-passport market size was valued at \$24.57 billion in 2019, and is projected to reach \$125.13 billion by 2028, growing at a CAGR of 27.5% from 2021 to 2028. Key players are 4G Identity Solutions, CardLogix Corporation, Ask Media Group, LLC, Entrust Corporation, Eastcompeace Technology Co., Ltd., Infineon Technologies AG, HID Global Corporation, Safran, Muhlbauer Group, and Thales Group. Target customers are private/public organisations, citizens, and companies.
EA3	QBE	AI-powered Continuous Behavioural Authentication	The global behavioural biometrics market size was valued at USD 0.87 billion in 2019 and is expected to expand at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 24.5% from 2020 to 2027. Key players are BehavioSec Inc., BioCatch and Fair Isaac Corporation. And the customers are private/public organisations, citizens, and companies.
EA4	RAPI	Non-Obtrusive and Safe X-Ray Technologies	The global X-ray Security Scanner Market was valued at USD 2.73 billion in 2020 and is expected to reach USD 4.07 billion by 2026 and work at a

Exploitable Asset	Owner	Description	Market Potential
		for Vehicle Scanning	CAGR of 6.88% over the forecast period (2021-2026). Key players are Rapiscan, L3 Security and Detection Systems, Astrophysics, Westminster International and Smiths. Target customers are commercial, LEAs, Border Authorities, Aviation and Transportation.
EA5	ACC	UAV-Assisted Vehicle Scanning based on Thermal and High-resolution Cameras	The Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) Market size is expected to surpass around US\$ 36 billion by 2030 and is anticipated to grow at a CAGR of 14% from 2021 and 2030. Key players are General Atomics Aeronautical Systems, Northrop Grumman, Israel Aerospace, Elbit Systems, Parrot, SZ DJI Technology, Lockheed Martin, Thales, Go Pro, 3D Robotics and AeroVironment, among others. Target customers are citizens, private/public organisations including Border Authorities.
EA6	TEL	Faceless GDPR Compliant Travellers Counting	The global video surveillance market was valued at \$42.94 billion in 2019, and is projected to reach \$144.85 billion by 2027, registering a CAGR of 14.6% from 2020 to 2027. Key players are HKVISION, Bosch, Honeywell, Dahua, FLIR, Panasonic, Avigilon, Axis, Infinova, and Pelco. Target customers are Governments, enterprises, financial institutions, stadiums, and healthcare organisations.
EA7	SQD	Multi-Modal Fusion and Decision Support System	The global user & entity behaviour analytics market is predicted to touch USD 1,178.9 million at a 41.73% CAGR between 2020- 2027, states the recent Market Research Future (MRFR) analysis. Prospect customers government and especially border control authorities.

Exploitable Asset	Owner	Description	Market Potential
EA8	QBE, SQD	X-AI for Privacy and Trust Enhancement	The global AI governance market size to grow from USD 50 million in 2020 to USD 1,016 million by 2026, at a CAGR of 65.5% during the forecast period. Various factors rise in need for building trust in AI systems and growth in demand for transparency in AI decisions. Key players in the global AI governance market include Google, Microsoft, IBM, SAP. Target customers are private/public organisations.
EA9	SIM, THALES, QBE, VISB, QBE, TEL, RAPI, ACC, SQD	ODYSSEUS Platform	<p>ODYSSEUS Platform will bring an innovative Seamless Border Cross for travel facilitation, focusing on digital technology offering to citizens the appropriate tools to cross land and sea borders in a secure and seamless manner, without stopping.</p> <p>The platform is designed to facilitate the border authorities control process to ensure Identification and control of goods and people using properly Identification equipment as well as an enhancement of the current way of identity verification of travellers. The platform is also improving the productivity of the Border and coastguards Authorities by combining a set of different technologies.</p>

7.4 NON-COMMERCIAL EXPLOITATION PLANS

The non-commercial exploitation plans will be prepared by consortium members identifying the positive outcomes that will derive from the project but will not have a commercial purpose.

These plans will encompass an extensive and comprehensive array of activities, such as:

- Research and development,
- Publications,
- Training initiatives,
- Standardisation efforts,
- Planning.

Each facet of these plans will be thoughtfully considered, outlining the specific types of activities that will be undertaken, as well as their corresponding objectives and timelines.

Furthermore, the plans will also prioritize the identification and definition of target audiences, ensuring that the solution reaches the intended beneficiaries. The anticipated impact and benefits of the solution will be thoroughly assessed, with a focus on evaluating its potential to create positive and meaningful changes in the targeted domains.

This assessment will delve into both the short-term and long-term effects, providing a comprehensive understanding of the potential value and transformative effects the solution can offer.

In essence, the non-commercial exploitation plans will serve as a meticulous roadmap, guiding the consortium members in their pursuit of disseminating knowledge, fostering collaboration, and driving positive change.

7.4.1 Publication plan and open access

The publications are an important part of the communication and dissemination activities, but they are also serving the exploitation of the project results.

As was presented in sections 4.3 and 4.9, ODYSSEUS has a target of at least 10 papers/articles during its three years of implementation, published in proceedings & online in premium quality conferences and journals.

As of the end of October 2024, four articles have been published by the Consortium partners:

1. Monica Florea, Dana Oniga (2023). “Why Crossing Borders will no Longer be an Odyssey from 2025.” – *Stiinta & Tehnica Magazine*. [Link to publication](#)
2. Kacper Kubrak, Grigore M. Havârneanu (2023). “Railway security checks at the border between intrusive security technologies and fundamental traveller rights.” – *Open Research Europe*. [Link to publication](#)
3. N. Palaghias et al. (2024). “Seamless Identity Verification at Water and Land Borders.” – *IEEE*. This research is part of the Project ODYSSEUS. [Link to publication](#)
4. ODYSSEUS Project (2024). “Innovative Solutions to Enhance the Security of EU Borders.” – *Border Security Report, September/October 2024, page 42-48*. [BSRSepOct2024.pdf \(border-security-report.com\)](#)

Each publication acknowledges the ODYSSEUS project, and the details can be verified on the ODYSSEUS publications page [here](#).

The plan for the next period is to engage the consortium in preparing 1 more article by the end of 2024 in an open access journal such as IEEE or Springer, as

the possibility to publish a paper related to the oral presentation to the Springer Book Series “[Security Informatics and Law Enforcement](#)” following a peer-review process. At least five additional articles will be published in similar journals during 2025, disseminating the results of the project.

The first video of ODYSSEUS project premiered in August 2024 on the project's YouTube channel:

[Welcome to ODYSSEUS: Enhancing EU Border Management \(youtube.com\)](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=RocFp_VFCZ8)

Figure 21: Introductory video of ODYSSEUS Project

At mid-October 2024, the video had 120 views. The video is accessible also through the project's website:

[The Introductory Video of the ODYSSEUS Project is Live! - Odysseus Project](#)

Another important step for the project was to provide an Open access to its results. So far, a repository on ZENODO was created, where all materials that are not sensitive will be published: Articles, posters, flyers, etc.

The screenshot shows the Zenodo website interface. At the top, there is a search bar and navigation links for 'Communities' and 'My dashboard'. Below this, the 'ODYSSEUS PROJECT' is featured with its logo and a 'New upload' button. The main content area shows a search result for 'ODYSSEUS – de ce trecerea granițelor nu va mai fi o odisee din 2025' by Oniga, Dana; FLOREA, Monica, dated December 16, 2023, and marked as 'Open'. The page also includes filters for 'Versions', 'Access status', and 'Resource types', and a 'Sort by' dropdown menu set to 'Newest'.

Figure 22: Zenodo repository

As a first step towards making public the main result of the project- the ODYSSEUS platform, the project enrolled this result on Horizon Results Booster platform: [Horizon Results Booster](#), together with Flexi-Cross and TENSOR projects in May 2024.

In the framework of Service 1, Module A (Identifying and creating the portfolio of R&I project results), the “Pre-Assessment Questionnaire For Individual Project” was completed for ODYSSEUS Project. Together with the other projects within the group, the other steps of this module will be taken until the end of 2024, to obtain a portfolio of results that are suitable for joint dissemination.

More discussions with partners will follow and the Open Research Europe platform is considered to disseminate the ODYSSEUS platform, providing a resource for the public in light of the "open science" principle and taking in consideration that the some of the solutions developed by different partners might not be available for disclosure.

7.5 COMMERCIAL EXPLOITATION PLANS-UPDATED

The commercial exploitation plans will be formulated by consortium members who stand to benefit commercially from the solution developed, as they reach into exploring the identified exploitable assets.

These comprehensive plans will encompass a wide range of activities, each carefully designed to maximize the solution's potential for commercial success.

The plans will include an extensive list of activities that take into consideration the various critical aspects of business development and strategy. This will encompass the following activities:

- Conducting in-depth marketing analysis and formulating a robust business plan, which outlines the vision, objectives, and strategies for capturing market share and achieving sustainable growth.
- A comprehensive competition analysis will also be undertaken, evaluating the strengths and weaknesses of competing offerings to inform strategic positioning and differentiation.
- A thorough PESTEL analysis will be conducted to assess the external factors that may impact the solution's market penetration and profitability.
- A SWOT matrix will be designed, evaluating the solution's internal strengths and weaknesses, as well as external opportunities and threats, to further refine the commercialization approach.
- Market segmentation will be carried out to identify and target specific customer segments that hold the highest potential for adoption and revenue generation.
- A go-to-market strategy will be developed, outlining the steps and tactics required to effectively introduce the solution to the target market.
- A Joint Exploitation and Commercialisation Plan will be developed including all Key Exploitable Assets.

7.5.1 Joint Exploitation and Commercialisation Plan

The consortium is actively working together to finalize a joint exploitation and commercialization plan that will ensure the successful market deployment of the ODYSSEUS platform. The consortium is in the process of developing a cohesive plan that leverages the collective strengths and resources of all partners to maximize impact.

The main steps in this joint exploitation and commercialization plan are as follows:

1. Market analysis – deadline 31 October 2024

The consortium is conducting a detailed market analysis to assess similar competitors, market needs, and the overall landscape for the ODYSSEUS platform. This analysis will ensure that the platform's value proposition is well defined and aligned with market expectations, as presented in Annex 4: Questionnaire Exploitation Business Plan. At the same time both PEST and SWOT analysis of the Key Exploitable Assets are in progress.

2. Business model development – deadline 31 March 2025

Building upon the market analysis, the consortium will develop potential business models to ensure the commercial success of the ODYSSEUS solution. The models

will include financial projections, market segmentation, licensing potential, and feasibility studies.

3. Partner exploitation plans – deadline 31 March 2025

Each partner will produce a detailed exploitation plan outlining how they will benefit from the project results and how they will contribute to the overall sustainability of the ODYSSEUS platform. These plans will detail each partner's role in commercialization and their specific contributions to the platform's success.

4. Joint licensing agreements – deadline 31 December 2025

The consortium will pursue joint licensing agreements with all partners or in groups of similar scope technologies. By working together on these agreements, the partners will ensure the large-scale deployment of the ODYSSEUS platform, sharing both the risks and rewards of commercialization.

In summary, the commercial exploitation plans will serve as a comprehensive blueprint, crafted by consortium members who stand to benefit commercially, outlining a detailed roadmap for leveraging exploitable assets and guiding the solution's successful commercialisation journey.

8 CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable is part of the WP6 and contains details pertaining to the ODYSSEUS project's communication and dissemination activities throughout its first 6 months (January 2023 – June 2023). With the objective to disseminate the project's outcomes, an overview of the relevant communication tools and communication/dissemination efforts was provided.

Overall, we are able to state that our dissemination efforts are proceeding as planned after the first 6 months of the initiative. Daily dissemination and communication tasks are carried out at the project level, and partners are actively involved, the consortium's progress has been very visible.

We can track our progress and identify which initiatives still require effort and which have already met their objectives by keeping a close check on established communication and dissemination KPIs. The focus will now be on improving specific parts that require improvement.

The second deliverable on communication and dissemination activities (D6.3 Dissemination, Communication, Exploitation and Stakeholders Engagement Report - final) due in M36- December 2023 of the project will provide an additional update on the actions described and anticipated in this deliverable.

ANNEX 1: DISSEMINATION PROCEDURES

HORIZON-101073910– ODYSSEUS

Dissemination Procedures

ODYSSEUS

**Unobtrusive Technologies for Secure and Seamless Border Crossing for Travel
Facilitation**

DISSEMINATION PROCEDURES

Funded by the
European Union

ODYSSEUS has received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement N°101073910. Content reflects only the authors' view and European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

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1 DESCRIPTION AND PURPOSE

The participation of any Partner in an event as well as the performance of every dissemination & communication activity related to ODYSSEUS project has to be approved beforehand by the Project Coordinator, the Project Manager and the Project Security Advisory Board (SAB).

1.1 OBJECTIVES

The objectives of the Dissemination Procedures are to ensure:

- (i) Production of high-quality publications & presentations;
- (ii) Avoid overlaps or disclosure of restricted information;
- (iii) Consistency in presentation of the Project to both internal and external audiences;
- (iv) Monitor & Record dissemination activities in a sufficient way.

For effective and successful dissemination and communications activities, all partners need to be fully involved and pursue opportunities in:

- (i) Presenting project concept, ideas & findings in every available occasion.
- (ii) Publishing work at conference proceedings, scientific journals, and other publications.
- (iii) Initiate bilateral discussions - more effective than sending brochures, newsletters etc.
- (iv) Local dissemination activities to involve respective authorities, stakeholders and end-users are also encouraged.
- (v) Share project news and information in your social media accounts.
- (vi) Inform your media contacts about project advances.

All of the above need to be reported prior and post completion to the WP6 leader katerina.kokaliari@accelligence.tech (ACC) and ODYSSEUS Dissemination Manager nantia.skourti@accelligence.tech (ACC) in accordance with the Dissemination Procedures and using the relevant reporting templates.

The Dissemination Manager is responsible for examining all the provided information and material, initiating the approval process, and ensuring that all information is properly collected and presented through the project website and social media prior or after the completion of the activity.

2 STEP-BY-STEP PROCEDURES

2.1 APPROVAL PROCEDURE

(prior to the performance of the activity)

A. For every dissemination and communication activity:

1. Fill in the dissemination activities report template available [here](#).
2. Store your material (abstract, draft paper, poster, presentation etc.) to the Dissemination Requests [here](#);
3. Submit your dissemination request allowing for **minimum two weeks before submission** deadline by email to the Dissemination Manager (nantia.skourti@accelligence.tech, cc: katerina.kokaliari@accelligence.tech)
4. WP6 Leader/ Dissemination Manager has 2 days to react and send the request to Coordinator/ Project Manager/ Project Security Advisory Board (SAB) for approval, modification or rejection;
5. Coordinator/ Project Coordination Team (PCT)/ Project Security Advisory Board decision send to the Dissemination Manager **within five working days**; If no answer is received by the set deadline, then it may be considered as an approval;
6. WP6 Leader/ Dissemination Manager informs the initiator of the dissemination activity along with the involved partner(s) about the decision.

In case of:

- A. **Approval**: When approval is given through the WP6 Leader, the partner(s) is (are) free to proceed with the realization of the proposed dissemination activity;
- B. **Conflict/objection**: Any Project Security Advisory Board (SAB) member can reject the proposed dissemination activity if they have objections, related to overlaps or possible disclosure of restricted or confidential information concern the work performed in the different WPs. In case of conflict, the issue will be discussed among the coordinator, the project manager, the WP6 Leader and the involved partners**

***If a conflict is created or further material is needed then WP6 Leader/ Dissemination Manager informs the partner that modifications or additions are required. Then the material is proposed again to WP6 Leader/ Dissemination Manager and if significant changes (that might provoke conflicts among partners' interests) must be made, the previous procedure is followed.*

B. For already approved material:

If partners wish to present or release material already approved as public presentation and other communication material, then no formal approval is required.

The ODYSSEUS Dissemination Manager (nantia.skourti@accelligence.tech, cc: katerina.kokaliari@accelligence.tech) has to be informed. If there are no objections, then the Dissemination Manager notifies the authors to proceed with the dissemination activity.

C. For organisation of ODYSSEUS event:

In case a partner wishes to organise a workshop or special event related to ODYSSEUS, then the approval of WP6 Leader and the information of the Coordinator, Project Manager and the Project Security Advisory Board is also needed 2 months before the realisation of this type of dissemination activity.

2.2 REPORTING OF DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

(after the performance of the activity)

Within **ten working days** after the realisation of the dissemination activity/ participation at the relevant event, Partners should provide the Dissemination Manager with:

- (i) a fully completed Dissemination Report (template provided [here](#));
- (ii) the presented dissemination material (final paper, presentation, poster, press release etc.);
- (iii) snippets from the online media and social media presence;
- (iv) relevant photos from the event.

The filled-in report and all the material received will be archived by the Dissemination Manager [here](#). The Dissemination Manager will use the information to populate the activity on the project digital media and efficiently report it to the EC.

3 GUIDELINES FOR THE USE OF THE PROJECT LOGO & EU EMBLEM

According to the Article 17 of *ODYSSEUS* Grand Agreement, any dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic) must display the EU emblem and must include the following *acknowledgement text*:

“ODYSSEUS project has received funding from European Union’s Horizon Europe Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement N°101073910”.

For any communication activity, the EU emblem must be displayed, along with the phrase:

““ODYSSEUS project has received funding from European Union’s Horizon Europe Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement N°101073910”.

For infrastructure, equipment & major results, the EU emblem must be displayed along with the phrase:

““This [infrastructure][equipment][insert type of result] is part of the ODYSSEUS project that has received funding from European Union’s Horizon Europe Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement N°101073910”.

When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have the appropriate prominence.

European flag available [here](#).

Partners are prompted to consult these Dissemination Procedures together with the guidelines on use of the EU emblem and relevant text and contact the Dissemination Manager (nantia.skourti@accelligence.tech, cc: katerina.kokaliari@accelligence.tech) for any clarifications or questions they may have **PRIOR** to publishing and/or sharing and/or participating and/or undertaking a dissemination activity.

4 BRAND CONSISTENCY

4.1 PROJECT LOGO AND TEMPLATES

For any questions or clarifications, and prior to any sharing and/or publication of material, Partners are requested to contact the Dissemination Manager (nantia.skourti@accelligence.tech, cc: katerina.kokaliari@accelligence.tech) to assist them.

The project dissemination templates can be found in the repository.

For the purposes of the Project and for a coherent presentation of the deliverables, the WP6 leader and Dissemination Manager have prepared the relevant templates to be used by Partners in preparing their own work/deliverables.

Specifically, these include:

- [PowerPoint presentation template](#)
- [Dissemination activities report template](#)
- Press Release template

All templates can be found on the online repository of the Project and can be downloaded and edited by each Partner. Templates can be edited (to the extent permissible), however the general layout, formatting and style must be adhered to by all partners.

4.2 PROJECT WEBSITE & SOCIAL MEDIA ACCOUNTS

The Project's official website can be found at: <https://odysseusproject.eu/>

The website includes information on the project (general theme, description, and objectives) as well as information on the consortium, News Page and other publicly available information relevant to the Project.

Dissemination activities may also be shared and/or posted on the website, subject to their nature and/or information available.

Partners are requested to include the link to the project website in every announcement they make about ODYSSEUS to their individual websites and on other media (newsletters, e-blasts etc.) they may use to present it.

The official social media accounts of the Project are available on LinkedIn and Twitter.

https://twitter.com/@odysseus_heu

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/odysseusproject-heu/>

Partners’ achievements and dissemination activities will be shared on the official social media accounts of the Project, together with other relevant public information.

Partners are requested to keep an eye on the social media platforms of the project and share/re-share posts and/or other material to their own social media platforms.

When share information about the project on your individual social media accounts please ensure to use at least the following @tags and #hashtags:

FOR TWITTER:

[@odysseus_heu](#)

#HorizonEU, #odysseusproject

FOR LINKEDIN:

[@odysseusproject-heu](#)

#HorizonEU, #odysseusprojectheu

as well as any other hashtags that would be relevant to the post shared and which would increase activity and visibility to the official accounts of the Projects.

4.3 ENQUIRIES AND CONTACT DETAILS

Partners are encouraged to contact the Project Manager and/or the WP6 leader/ Dissemination Manager for any assistance or clarifications they may require.

Project Manager: Dana Oniga	dana.oniga@simavi.ro
WP6 leader: Katerina Kokaliari	katerina.kokaliari@accelligence.tech
Dissemination Manager: Nantia Skourti	nantia.skourti@accelligence.tech

ANNEX 2: PRESS RELEASE

Unobtrusive Technologies for Secure and Seamless
Border Crossing for Travel Facilitation

PRESS RELEASE

21 February 2023

Launch of EU-funded project “ODYSSEUS”

Better protection, faster identity verification at the border
with EU-funded project “ODYSSEUS”.

The newly launched ODYSSEUS European project is expected to improve border crossing experience for travelers and border authorities' staff, while maintaining security and monitoring of movements across land and sea EU external borders. The aim of this project is to support the safety and integrity of the European space, reducing illegal movements of people and goods across those borders, and protecting fundamental rights of travelers.

ODYSSEUS also aims to enhance customs and supply chain security through better prevention, detection, deterrence, and fight of illegal activities, involving flows of goods across EU external border crossing points and through the supply chain, minimising disruption to trade flows.

The new project will provide a holistic framework for improving border checks performed by the authorities and facilitate travelling for citizens. A combination of strong multi-behavioral and biometric continuous user identity verification mechanisms will ensure the identification of the citizens, allowing them to cross the border without any interruption or queue. In the meantime, a novel luggage and baggage check will allow citizens' vehicles and cargos to be remotely checked on the land border in terms of goods and thus speed up the border check processes in a secure and reliable manner. The ODYSSEUS platform will be applicable for both land and water scenarios including on the road, in a maritime port, and in the train.

ODYSSEUS has received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement N°101073910.

Unobtrusive Technologies for Secure and Seamless Border Crossing for Travel Facilitation

The ODYSSEUS solution will be tested, validated, and demonstrated in three real operational scenarios selected for their high societal, economic and security impact on the EU citizens and the Border Authorities. The foreseen scenarios include seamless border crossing on Land, Sea, and Train. Pre-pilot activities will also take place, including ODYSSEUS technical verification, pilot planning and setup as well as end-user recruitment.

WHAT ARE THE MAIN OBJECTIVES OF THE PROJECT?

- o **DESIGN** and **DEVELOP** a unifying platform that enables seamless, fully non-stop border crossing in a highly secure manner, assisting Law Enforcement Agencies (LEA) with automated, reliable, and accurate border checks, while improving the travelling experience for EU citizens in a privacy-preserving way.
- o **ADVANCE** the identification and control capabilities of Border Authorities through robust and reliable identity verification mechanisms introducing an EU mobile (virtual) passport protected by continuous behavioral authentication.
- o **IMPROVE** border control checks without stopping cargos and vehicles through safe, unobtrusive, and portable screening based on X-ray backscatter technology, UAV-assisted image processing and AI-based data analytics.
- o **VALIDATE** the effectiveness of the proposed ODYSSEUS platform through its demonstration in real-life environments with the active engagement and training of security practitioners in two diverse landscapes and various operational environments (inside a train, on the road, onboard a ship in a port area).
- o **SPEED UP** the rapid uptake by relevant security stakeholders of the ODYSSEUS innovations through wide communication, scientific dissemination and targeted commercial exploitation activities coupled with contributions to relevant standardisation bodies.

ODYSSEUS is a 3-year, Horizon funded project that began in January 2023 and will last until December 2025. It involves 14 partners from Romania, Portugal, Greece, Cyprus, Belgium, Czech Republic, Italy, France, Bulgaria, Slovakia, Moldova, and the United Kingdom. [SIMAVI](#), [VISB](#), [QBE](#), [TEL](#), [RAPI](#), [ACCELI](#), [SQD](#), [THALES](#), [ISIG](#), [IGPF](#), [CDBP](#), [BBA](#), [IGPF_MAI](#) and [UIC](#). SIMAVI will lead the consortium and the project activities, to successfully accomplish the project objectives and Key Performance Indicators.

ODYSSEUS has received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement N°101073910.

Unobtrusive Technologies for Secure and Seamless Border Crossing for Travel Facilitation

The ODYSSEUS project has received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement N°101073910. The project has a duration of 36 months, with total budget of 4.59 million euro, of which 3.45 million euro are funded by the European Union.

The project kick-off meeting took place in Bucharest on January 26th and 27th, 2023, and welcomed over 20 attendees committed to working together to develop prototype technologies, illustrate use cases, and produce a valuable and deployable solution.

Further information can be found at: www.odysseusproject.eu which is currently under construction but will be online soon.

FOLLOW ODYSSEUS JOURNEY AND KEEP UP WITH NEW DEVELOPMENTS AND UPCOMING RESULTS.

Join ODYSSEUS's community on Twitter ([@odysseus_heu](https://twitter.com/odysseus_heu)) & on LinkedIn ([@odysseusproject-heu](https://www.linkedin.com/company/odysseusproject-heu)).

Disclaimer: The content of this document reflects only the authors' view, and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

ODYSSEUS has received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement N°101073910.

ANNEX 3: ODYSSEUS STANDARDISATION SURVEY

ODYSSEUS Standardisation Survey

This Survey has been developed within the ODYSSEUS project, to collect information from **all project partners** as a baseline for the development of the ODYSSEUS standardisation strategy.

The results will be reported in D6.1 (reviewed version - to be submitted by June 15th 2024).

The deadline to provide your answers is **May 15th 2024**.

ODYSSEUS Standardisation Survey

Section 1: Identification of respondent

* 1. Identification of respondent

Organisation	<input type="text"/>
Name and Surname	<input type="text"/>
E-mail	<input type="text"/>

ODYSSEUS Standardisation Survey

Section 2: Innovations Identification

2. Which innovations within ODYSSEUS do you believe have potential for standardisation?

Innovation 1	<input type="text"/>
Innovation 2	<input type="text"/>
Innovation 3	<input type="text"/>

* 3. How do you envision these innovations aligning with existing standards or standardisation efforts in the industry?

	Limited alignment	Moderate alignment	Strong alignment	Not sure
Innovation 1	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Innovation 2	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Innovation 3	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

ODYSSEUS Standardisation Survey

Section 3: Standardisation objectives

4. What specific standardisation objectives do you see ODYSSEUS achieving with each innovation?

Innovation 1

Innovation 2

Innovation 3

5. Other objectives (please specify)

ODYSSEUS Standardisation Survey

Section 4: Identification of standardisation opportunities (international and national level)

For each innovation (indicated in Q2), please indicate the existing relevant standards connected (both at the international and national level):
(for each standard please provide the following information: number of standard, full name, link)

6. Innovation 1

Standard 1

Standard 2

Standard 3

7. Innovation 2

Standard 1

Standard 2

Standard 3

8. Innovation 3

Standard 1

Standard 2

Standard 3

For each innovation (indicated in Q2), please indicate the relevant standards under development connected (both at the international and national level):
(for each standard please provide the following information: number of standard, full name, link)

9. Innovation 1

Standard 1

Standard 2

Standard 3

10. Innovation 2

Standard 1

Standard 2

Standard 3

11. Innovation 3

Standard 1

Standard 2

Standard 3

12. Please indicate any other relevant standard:

ODYSSEUS Standardisation Survey

Section 5: Identification of forums and bodies

*** 13. What criteria do you suggest for selecting relevant standardisation forums and bodies for submission of contributions?**

- Alignment with project objectives
- Relevance to industry standards
- Track record of influence
- Global reach
- Reputation and credibility
- Other (please specify)

14. Are there specific forums or bodies you believe we should prioritize?

- 1.
- 2.
- 3.
- 4.
- 5.

*** 15. Are you participating in the working groups/ standardisation committees responsible for the development/update of the ODYSSEUS relevant standards?**

- Yes
- No
- I participate to other working groups/standardisation committees (please specify)

ODYSSEUS Standardisation Survey

16. Please specify which one(s):

17. Do you have any contacts with the organisations responsible for the development of these standards?

- Yes
- No

ODYSSEUS Standardisation Survey

Section 6: Partners involvement

* 18. As an ODYSSEUS partner, how do you perceive your role in the standardisation process?

- Providing technical expertise
- Contributing to documentation elaboration
- Participating in standardization forums
- No contribution
- Other (please specify)

* 19. What expertise do you bring in terms of standardisation efforts?

- Technical knowledge
- Industry experience
- Regulatory understanding
- No expertise
- Other (please specify)

ODYSSEUS Standardisation Survey**Section 7: End-user Engagement/Identification of stakeholders**

* 20. How do you propose we engage end-users in the standardisation process?

- Conducting surveys
- Conducting in-depth interviews
- Involving end-users in workshops/focus groups
- Other (please specify)

* 21. What insights or perspectives do you think end-users can provide?

- Usability requirements
- Security concerns
- Regulatory compliance needs
- Other (please specify)

ODYSSEUS Standardisation Survey**Section 8: Submission plan**

* 22. Do you plan to submit contributions to relevant forums/bodies?

- Yes
- No
- I do not know yet

ODYSSEUS Standardisation Survey

* 23. Please provide details on the planned contribution:

* 24. What timeline do you propose for submitting your contribution to the relevant forums and bodies?

- June 2024
- September 2024
- December 2024
- March 2025
- June 2025
- Other (please specify)

* 25. Which kind of support do you foresee from other project partners:

- Provision of technical expertise
- Contribution to documentation elaboration
- Review of documentation
- Formal approval
- Other (please specify)

ODYSSEUS Standardisation Survey

Section 9: Monitoring and evaluation

* 26. How should we monitor and evaluate the progress of ODYSSEUS standardisation strategy?

- Regular progress reports
- Key performance indicators (KPIs)
- Feedback from end-users/stakeholders
- Other (please specify)

* 27. What indicators or metrics would you suggest to use to assess success?

- Number of contributions submitted
- Adoption of standards by industry
- Recognition from regulatory bodies
- Other (please specify)

28. Please provide any other comments and/or suggestions:

**ANNEX 4: QUESTIONNAIRE EXPLOITATION
BUSINESS PLAN**

#	Question
1	What is the product?
2	What market gap are you covering?
3	Who buys the product (type of clients, name of main clients, countries, etc)?
4	What is the size of the market (global, regional)?
5	What are your main competitors?
6	What are the main competitive advantages?
7	What is the reference pricing and cost per product?

ODYSSEUS

Unobtrusive Technologies for Secure and Seamless Border Crossing for Travel Facilitation

The Members of the ODYSSEUS Consortium:

Short Name	Country	Short Name	Country
SIMAVI	Romania	ISIG	Italy
VISB	Portugal	RBP	Romania
QBE	Greece	CDBP	Bulgaria
TEL	Greece	BBA	Slovakia
ACC	Cyprus	IGPF MAI	Moldova
SQD	Belgium	UIC	France
THALES	Czechia	RAPI	UK

Contact:

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monica.florea@simavi.ro	dana.oniga@simavi.ro